

Deliverable number 2.5 – AtlantECO-MAPS

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
MAPS 1	<p>Lead authors: Meike Vogt (ETHZ), Fabio Benedetti (ETHZ), Daniele de Angelis (UNIROMA), Luigi Maiorano (UNIROMA)</p> <p>Contributing authors: Dominic Eriksson (ETHZ), Nielja Knecht (ETHZ), Giacomo Poli (ETHZ), Xinhang Li (ETHZ), Olivier Jaillon (CEA/GENOSCOPE), Paul Frémont (CEA/ GENOSCOPE), Fabien Lombard (SU), Lionel Guidi (SU), Erik Van Sebille (UU), Marion Gehlen (CEA), Germain Benard (CEA), Thomas Frölicher (UBern), Tim Collart (SBE)</p>		12.01.2024
MAPS 2	<p>Lead authors: Meike Vogt (ETHZ), Théophile Sanchez (ETHZ), Paula Huber (UFSCar)</p> <p>Contributing authors: Marinna Gaudin (LS2N), Roniel Freitas-Oliveira (UFSCar), Dominic Eriksson (ETHZ), Samuel Chaffron (CNRS/UNantes), Damien Eveillard (CNRS/UNantes), Alexandre Schickele (ETHZ), Corentin Clerc (ETHZ/IPSL)</p>	<p>Addition of 6 new mapped products:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Picozoa global habitat suitability and richness from Huber et al. (2024) 2. Projected Habitat suitability for the co-occurrence of inferred ecological associations as reported in M.Gaudin et al. (2024) 3. Functional (KOs) and Taxonomic (mOTUs) Diversity from De Angelis et al., in preparation (2025) 4. Operational Protein Units (OPUs) from Huber et al. (2024) 5. Variations in the latitudinal diversity gradients of the ocean microbiome 6. Current and projected functional diversity of copepod communities as reported in Benedetti et al. (2025) 	10.09.2025
MAPS	Stéphane Pesant	Reorganising & harmonising AtlantECO-MAPS descriptions, and submission of AtlantECO-MAPS to SEANOE	25.02.2026

2 Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the latest developments in AtlantECO-MAPS, a key exploitable result of the AtlantECO project, developed under Task 2.3 ‘Map microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere, carbon flux and derived ecosystem structure and functions’. AtlantECO-MAPS uses state-of-the-art species distribution models that were carefully calibrated to account for spatiotemporal biases typical of marine ecosystem data. It generates maps at global scale, using discrete observations delivered in AtlantECO-BASE (D2.1 and D2.3) and assembled by:

Task 2.2.1 ‘Microbiome data from traditional microscopy (presence-absence, abundance and biomass)’,

Task 2.2.2 ‘Microbiome data from state-of-the-art optical/imaging analysis’,

Task 2.2.3 ‘Microbiome and plastisphere data from state-of-the-art genetic analyses’,

Task 2.2.4 ‘Nano-, micro and macroplastics data from state-of-the-art sampling methods’, and

Task 2.2.5 ‘Carbon flux data estimated from high resolution bio-optical sensors’.

This second version of AtlantECO-MAPS (D2.5) extends the first version (D2.3) with the addition of 6 new mapped products:

1. Picozoa global habitat suitability and richness from Huber et al. (2024)
2. Projected Habitat suitability for the co-occurrence of inferred ecological associations as reported in M.Gaudin et al. (2024)
3. Functional (KOs) and Taxonomic (mOTUs) Diversity from De Angelis et al., in preparation (2025)
4. Operational Protein Units (OPUs) from Huber et al. (2024)
5. Variations in the latitudinal diversity gradients of the ocean microbiome
6. Current and projected functional diversity of copepod communities as reported in Benedetti et al. (2025)

This deliverable also reports on data visualisation apps and modelling pipelines specifically developed for the AtlantECO project and Task 2.3.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction & Methodology

In recent years, the number of marine observations of plankton occurrence, biomass, taxonomic or functional diversity, traits and/or species distributions has increased exponentially. However, marine plankton observations remain sparse in space and time, making the interpretation of raw data prone to large uncertainties (Righetti et al., 2023). The statistical exploitation of the underlying relationships between biological target variables and environmental predictors known, or suspected, to constrain the realised environmental niche or spatiotemporal distribution of the target, commonly referred to as ‘species distribution modelling’ or ‘niche modelling’, can help alleviate issues related to data scarcity and sampling biases. Such statistical data analysis can also be used to model and extrapolate (i.e., map) observation-driven information to under-sampled ocean regions or to potential future states of the ocean and climate. To this end, models must be calibrated to explicitly account for data limitations, as well as rigorously evaluated based on multiple evaluation metrics. In the current deliverable AtlantECO-MAPS, we present a compilation of biological target variables extrapolated to the global scale using state-of-the-art species distribution models and subsets of the ocean microbiome data delivered in AtlantECO-BASE (Vogt et al. 2023), as well as additional model outputs produced in related species modelling activities. These extrapolated maps may be of use for a wide stakeholder community, including marine ecosystem modellers, remote sensing scientists, non-academic stakeholders such as policy makers, ecosystem managers and conservationists, as well as members of the education sector (teachers, museums).

Figure 1: Modelling pathway for the extrapolation of biological and other AtlantECO target variables to the global scale using species distribution modelling (Benedetti et al. 2021).

Here, we use established and newly developed methodologies to extrapolate the publicly available geo-referenced data on the marine microbiome and its functions and stressors/pollutants gathered in AtlantECO-BASE1 and -BASE2 (Vogt et al., 2023) across taxonomic groups and sampling methods to generate global data products (for use in statistical mapping and extrapolation), with a particular emphasis on the

Atlantic Ocean (All-Atlantic Microbiome Atlas; AtlantECO-MAPS1, D2.3; Vogt et al. 2023). We explore marine microbiome data from traditional (task 2.2.1), imaging (task 2.2.2), and genetic (task 2.2.3) sampling methods, as well as information on ecosystem functioning (carbon fluxes, task 2.2.4) and ecosystem pollutants (plastics, task 2.2.3). Observational data informing on the presence-absence, abundance, biomass and diversity of the marine microbiome are available for use in WP3 (marine ecosystem health and services), WP5 (advances in systems ecology), WP6 (advances in model predictability), comparable with assessments carried out in WP7 (ecosystem change) and will serve as inputs for the activities in WP8 (predictions of and for ecosystem services). We also serve a range of data products generated by AtlantECO partners in other projects that are of relevance for AtlantECO.

All geo-referenced data are provided as a collection of NetCDF files, and a collection of CMIP6 simulations for future projections is also made available (section 4.11; AtlantECO-CMIP6). A range of visualisation tools has been created to showcase our outputs for communication, capacity building, and outreach (section 4.10). This second version of AtlantECO-MAPS (D2.5) extends the collection of mapped datasets gathered in AtlantECO-MAPS1 (D2.3). All output products have been made publicly available to partners, sister projects and the wider science community (WP10) and are disseminated through the KER tool kit on the AtlantECO legacy website, and the AtlantECO GeoNode.

3.1 Modelling pathways, quality control and documentation

Species distribution models for the extrapolation of geo-referenced data in space and time were developed in accordance with community accepted standards for design and quality control procedures developed for the modelling of scarce and biased data (task 2.1), as detailed in Righetti et al. (2023), and have been documented in agreement with current community standards (Zurell et al., 2020). In the case of species distribution products that were obtained from non-AtlantECO publications, the methodology is specified in respective publications.

3.2 Data description and access

A comprehensive description of the 20 AtlantECO-MAPS collections is provided in Section 4. Each collection is archived, citable and accessible at SEANOE - Sea Scientific Open Data Publication (<https://www.seanoe.org/>) and a selection of maps are showcased on the AtlantECO GeoNode platform (<https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>). Summary Table I provides an overview of the topic covered by each collection as well as links to the corresponding data publication on SEANOE and the associated journal article. Summary Table II provides more specific details about the mapping, modelling and output files for each collection.

4 AtlantECO-MAPS

Summary Table I - AtlantECO-MAPS access & associated scientific publications

MAPS #	AtlantECO-MAPS title	MAPS published at SEANOE (url:doi)	Associated Scientific publication (url:doi)
MAPS #1	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 341 species of autotrophs and 504 species of heterotrophs in surface waters, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012-2031) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Benedetti et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110714	Benedetti et al. (2021) https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x
MAPS #2	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 326 species of autotrophs and 517 species of heterotrophs in the surface mixed layer, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary and future (2012-2100) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Eriksson et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110715	Eriksson et al. (in preparation)
MAPS #3	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 14 species of nitrogen-fixing taxa (diazotrophs) in epipelagic waters (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Eriksson et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110716	Eriksson et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.32942/X2Z323
MAPS #4	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 374 Single-cell and Metagenome Assembled Genomes (SMAGs) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Delmont et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110717	Delmont et al. (2022) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100123
MAPS #5	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 53 Operational Taxonomic Units of the phylum Picozoa (pOTUs) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Huber et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110718	Huber et al. (2024) https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-024-01874-1
MAPS #6	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Abundance of 17 groups of autotrophs in the surface mixed layer, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Crédeville et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110719	Crédeville et al. (2025) https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.10.25.684415
MAPS #7	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 20 Operational Protein Units (OPUs) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Huber et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110720	Huber et al. (in preparation)

MAPS #	AtlantECO-MAPS title	MAPS published at SEANOE (url:doi)	Associated Scientific publication (url:doi)
MAPS #8	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Co-occurrence of 57,082 pairs of taxa in surface waters (10 m), projected under contemporary (2006-15) and future (2015-2100) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Gaudin et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110721	Gaudin et al. (2024) https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2023.0169
MAPS #9	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Species richness of autotrophs in the surface mixed layer, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012-2031) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 538 taxa including species of diatoms, dinoflagellates and coccolithophores.	Righetti et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110723	Righetti et al. (2019) https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.aau6253
MAPS #10	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Species richness of three taxonomic groups of autotrophs, and eleven taxonomic groups of heterotrophs in surface waters, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of species belonging to each taxonomic group.	Benedetti et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110724	Benedetti et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbad044
MAPS #11	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Species richness of nitrogen-fixing taxa (diazotrophs) in epipelagic waters (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 14 species of cyanobacterial and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs.	Eriksson et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110725	Eriksson et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.32942/X2Z323
MAPS #12	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Richness of the phylum Picozoa in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 53 Operational Taxonomic Units of the phylum Picozoa (pOTUs).	Huber et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110726	Huber et al. (2024) https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-024-01874-1
MAPS #13	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Taxonomic and functional diversity of prokaryotes in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 1,210 marker gene-based Operational Taxonomic Units of prokaryotes (mOTUs).	De Angelis et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110727	De Angelis et al. (in preparation)
MAPS #14	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Taxonomic diversity of prokaryotes (bacteria and archaea) in the surface mixed layer, projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of marker gene-based Operational Taxonomic Units of prokaryotes (mOTUs).	Eriksson et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110728	Eriksson et al. (2025) https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.10.13.682024
MAPS #15	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Taxonomic and functional diversity of copepods in surface waters (0-10 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012–2031) and future, end-of-century (2081–2100) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Benedetti et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110729	Benedetti et al. (2025) https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70094
MAPS #16	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Carbon biomass of two eukaryotic calcifying taxa (pteropoda and foraminifera) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Knecht et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110730	Knecht et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GB007685

MAPS #	AtlantECO-MAPS title	MAPS published at SEANOE (url:doi)	Associated Scientific publication (url:doi)
MAPS #17	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Carbon biomass of 20 taxonomic groups of zooplankton in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m) and mesopelagic layer (200-500), available as annual averages projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.	Drago et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110731	Drago et al. (2022) https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.894372
MAPS #18	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Climato-Genomic Provinces projected under contemporary (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) environmental conditions.	Frémont et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110732	Frémont et al. (2022) https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8
MAPS #19	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index comparing climato-genomic provinces projected under contemporary (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) environmental conditions.	Frémont et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/110733	Frémont et al. (2022) https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8
MAPS #20	Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Concentration of microplastic in surface waters, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental and anthropogenic predictors.	Poli et al. (2026) https://doi.org/10.17882/112182	Poli (2023) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245292

Summary Table II - AtlantECO-MAPS specifications

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
MAPS #1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 50,700 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 845 [species] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [presence probability (0-1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2012-2031)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [surface waters] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2012-2031) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 19 predictors (see list of associated references below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 845 • <i>File size</i>: 15 MB/file = total 12.7 GB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 13,353,120 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 843 [species] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [presence probability (0-1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 88 years [2012-2100] • <i>Climate scenario(s)</i>: 3 [RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [surface mixed layer] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary and future (2012-2100) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Random Forest (RF) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 19 predictors (see list of associated references below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 Earth System Models (ESMs) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM-CM5) ○ Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model (GFDL-ESM2M) • Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace Climate Model 5A-Long Range (IPSL-CM5A-LR)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 74,184 • <i>File size</i>: 14.8 MB/file = total 1.1 TB • <i>File format</i>: zarr file (*.zarr)
MAPS #3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 672 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 14 [species] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [presence probability (0-1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 4 [mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2012) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Random Forest (RF) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 16 predictors (see list and associated references below) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 14 • <i>File size</i>: 12 MB/file = total 168 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic waters (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	
MAPS #4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 9,646 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 374 [SMAGS] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [presence probability (0-1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 1 [mean] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 2 [present day (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 13 [monthly + 12 month-average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2012-2031) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) ○ Random Forest (RF) ○ Neural Networks (NN) ○ General Additive Models (GAM) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 7 predictors (see list and associated references below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: ensemble of 6 Earth System Models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CESM1-BGC (Gent et al., 2011) ○ GFDL-ESM2G & GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013) ○ HadGEM2-ES (Collins et al., 2011) ○ IPSL-CM5A-LR & IPSL-CM5A-MR (Dufresne et al., 2013) ○ MPI-ESM-LR & MPI-ESM-MR (Giorgetta et al., 2013) ○ NorESM1-ME (Bentsen et al., 2013) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 748 • <i>File size</i>: 2.04 MB/file = total 1.53 GB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 265 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 53 [pOTUs] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [presence probability (0-1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 5 [minimum, maximum, average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [multi-year average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2017) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Artificial Neural Network (ANN) ○ Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) ○ Random Forest (RF) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 8 predictors (see list and associated references below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 53 • <i>File size</i>: 1.3 MB/file = total 66 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 34 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 17 [16 clades and total] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [abundance (cells/L)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 2 [mean, standard deviation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [annual climatology] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2012) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: bagging regression trees ensemble models • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 7 predictors (see list below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 1 • <i>File size</i>: not provided • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0 - mixed layer depth)] 		
MAPS #7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 40 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 20 [OPUs] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [presence probability (0-1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 2 [average, coefficient of variation] • <i>Time period(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [multi-year average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2017) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Artificial Neural Network (ANN) ○ Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) ○ Random Forest (RF) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 8 predictors (see list and associated references below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 20 • <i>File size</i>: not provided • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 74,599 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 57,082 [pairwise species associations]* • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [co-occurrence (1, 0, -1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 1 [value from 1 model] • <i>Time period(s)</i>: 2 [contemporary (2006-2015) and future (2015-2100)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [multi-year average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [surface waters (10 m)] <p>*a subset of 17,517 pairwise species associations were mapped under future conditions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2012-2031) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: 1 model <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Random Forest (RF) (<i>used</i>) ○ Gradient Tree Boosting (GTB) (<i>tested but not used</i>) ○ Support Vector Machine (SVM) (<i>tested but not used</i>) ○ Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) (<i>tested but not used</i>) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 predictors (see list below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: IPSL RCP 4.5 projections: from 2015 to 2100 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 2 • <i>File size</i>: 294 MB and 181 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 12 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 1 [autotrophs] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [species richness] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 1 [ensemble mean] • <i>Time period(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2012-2031)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [surface mixed layer] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2012-2031) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Random Forest (RF) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 19 predictors (see list of associated references below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 1 • <i>File size</i>: 3 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 1,680 [global maps] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 28

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 14 [functional groups of species] ● <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [species richness] ● <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 5 [minimum, maximum, mean, median and standard deviation] ● <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 2 [contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100)] ● <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] ● <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] ● <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [surface waters] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) ● <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 19 predictors (see list of associated references below) ● <i>Climate model(s)</i>: ensemble of 5 Earth System Models (ESMs) forced by RCP8.5 scenario <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Community Earth System Model version 1 (CESM1, POP-BEC) ○ Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model with Modular Ocean Model version 4 (GFDL-ESM2M; MOM-TOPAZ) ○ Institut Pierre Simon Laplace Climate Model version 5A-LR (IPSL-CM5A-LR; NEMO-PISCES) ○ Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM- CM5; NEMO-PISCES) ○ Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate version 5 (MIROC5; MRI.COM-MEM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>File size</i>: 14.9 MB/file = total 416 MB ● <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 48 [global maps] ● <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 1 [nitrogen-fixing taxa (diazotrophs)] ● <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [species richness] ● <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 4 [minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation] ● <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)] ● <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] ● <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] ● <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic waters (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2012) ● <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Random Forest (RF) ● <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 16 predictors (see list and associated references below) ● <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 1 ● <i>File size</i>: 12 MB ● <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 5 [global maps] ● <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 1 [Picozoa] ● <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [species richness] ● <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 5 [minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation] ● <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2017) ● <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Artificial Neural Network (ANN) ○ Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) ○ Random Forest (RF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 1 ● <i>File size</i>: 0.52 MB ● <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [multi-year average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 9 predictors (see list below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable <p>*models were calibrated across the 0-5 and 500 depth range</p>	
MAPS #13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 4 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 1 [prokaryotes] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 4 [Shannon taxonomic diversity, Simpson taxonomic diversity, Shannon functional diversity, Simpson functional diversity] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 1 [mean] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [multi-year average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2017) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Artificial Neural Network (ANN) ○ Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) ○ Random Forest (RF) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 6 predictors (see list below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 4 • <i>File size</i>: 0.275 MB/file = total 1.1 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 2 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: not provided [bacteria & archaea domains & classes] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 3 [taxonomic richness, Shannon diversity, chao1 diversity] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 2 [mean, standard deviation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: not provided [annual] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic waters (0-mixed layer depth)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2012) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 6 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Random Forest (RF) ○ MLP ○ BRT ○ SVM • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 16 predictors (see list and associated references below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: not provided • <i>File size</i>: not provided MB/file = total 302 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 1,080 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 2 [copepod species & copepod functional traits] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 9 [Species richness, functional richness, standardized effect size of functional richness, functional dispersion, functional divergence, functional evenness, trait dissimilarity, trait turnover and trait nestedness] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2012-2031) & future, end-of-century (2081-2100) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 3 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generalized Linear Models (GLM) ○ Generalized Additive Models (GAM) ○ Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 6 predictors (see list below) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 2 • <i>File size</i>: 136.7 MB/file = total 273.4 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 2 [contemporary (2012-2031) & end of century (2081-2100)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] WGS84 reference system • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [surface waters (0-10 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: ensemble of 5 Earth System Models (ESMs) forced by RCP8.5 scenario <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Community Earth System Model version 1 (CESM1, POP-BEC) ○ Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model with Modular Ocean Model version 4 (GFDL-ESM2M; MOM-TOPAZ) ○ Institut Pierre Simon Laplace Climate Model version 5A-LR (IPSL-CM5A-LR; NEMO-PISCES) ○ Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM- CM5; NEMO-PISCES) ○ Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate version 5 (MIROC5; MRI.COM-MEM) 	
MAPS #16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 120 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 2 [pteropoda and foraminifera] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [carbon biomass*] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200m)] <p>* units for are mg C m⁻³ for pteropoda and µg C m⁻³ for foraminifera</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2017) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 5 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ General Linear Models (GLM) ○ General Additive Models (GAM) ○ Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) ○ Random Forest (RF) ○ Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 predictors (see list below) • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 2 • <i>File size</i>: 18 MB/file = total 36 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 60 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 20 [taxonomic groups] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [carbon biomass (mgC/m3)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 3 [mean, standard error, standard deviation] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [annual average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m) or pelagic layer (0-500 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2017) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: 1 model <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 9 predictors • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 20 • <i>File size</i>: 400-900 KB/file = total 13.3 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
MAPS #18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 54 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 27 [climato genomic provinces] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [presence (0 or 1)] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 1 [projected value] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 2 [contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [10 year average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: comparison of contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099; RCP8.5) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) ○ Random Forest (RF) ○ Neural Networks (NN) ○ General Additive Models (GAM) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 7 predictors • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: ensemble of 6 Earth System Models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CESM1-BGC (Gent et al., 2011) ○ GFDL-ESM2G & GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013) ○ HadGEM2-ES (Collins et al., 2011) ○ IPSL-CM5A-LR & IPSL-CM5A-MR (Dufresne et al., 2013) ○ MPI-ESM-LR & MPI-ESM-MR (Giorgetta et al., 2013) ○ NorESM1-ME (Bentsen et al., 2013) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 54 • <i>File size</i>: 2 MB/file = total 108 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 3 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 1 [climato genomic provinces dissimilarity] • <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index] • <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 1 [projected value] • <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [comparison of contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099)] • <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 1 [comparison of two 10 year average] • <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 3 [360x180 (1x1 degree), Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs), fisheries areas] • <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [epipelagic layer (0 - 200 m)] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: comparison of contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 4 models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) ○ Random Forest (RF) ○ Neural Networks (NN) ○ General Additive Models (GAM) • <i>Environmental predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 7 predictors • <i>Climate model(s)</i>: ensemble of 6 Earth System Models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CESM1-BGC (Gent et al., 2011) ○ GFDL-ESM2G & GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013) ○ HadGEM2-ES (Collins et al., 2011) ○ IPSL-CM5A-LR & IPSL-CM5A-MR (Dufresne et al., 2013) ○ MPI-ESM-LR & MPI-ESM-MR (Giorgetta et al., 2013) ○ NorESM1-ME (Bentsen et al., 2013) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 3 • <i>File size</i>: 2 MB/file = total 6 MB • <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)
MAPS #20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of map(s)</i>: 12 [global maps] • <i>Mapped Entity(ies)</i>: 1 [microplastics] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Time period(s)</i>: contemporary (2005-2017) • <i>Habitat Suitability Model(s)</i>: ensemble of 5 models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Number of file(s)</i>: 1 • <i>File size</i>: 60 MB

MAPS #	Map(s) specifications	Model(s) specifications	File(s) specifications
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Mapped Variable(s)</i>: 1 [concentration (#/km², log10 transformed)]● <i>Statistic(s)</i>: 1 [minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation]● <i>Time periods(s)</i>: 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]● <i>Temporal grid(s)</i>: 12 [monthly]● <i>Horizontal grid(s)</i>: 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]● <i>Vertical grid(s)</i>: 1 [surface]	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ General Linear Model (GLM)○ General Additive Model (GAM)○ Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)○ Random Forest (RF)○ Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)● <i>Environmental & anthropogenic predictor(s)</i>: ensemble of 30 predictors (see list below)● <i>Climate model(s)</i>: not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>File format</i>: NetCDF (*.nc)

4.1 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #1

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 341 species of autotrophs and 504 species of heterotrophs in surface waters, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012-2031) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides species-level monthly fields of habitat suitability indices (HSI, ranging between 0 and 1; also called ‘presence probability’) for phytoplankton and zooplankton, for the contemporary time period. Each NetCDF file records the monthly: minimum (Min), maximum (Max), mean, median and the standard deviation (Stdev) of the species-specific HSI predictions issued from three species distribution models. The species distribution models used to generate the maps relied on background data were based on a “total target group approach”. These species distribution models were trained on species-level georeferenced occurrence (presence-only) data collectively gathered in the ZooBase dataset. Phytoplankton species (n=341) were separated from zooplankton species (n=504) on the basis that these two categories constitute two broadly-defined trophic levels (i.e., primary and secondary producers, respectively).

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Monthly mean ensemble habitat suitability indices (HSI) for Oithona parvula.

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, presence, ocean microbiome, autotrophs, heterotrophs, phytoplankton, zooplankton, contemporary climate conditions
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** The species-level maps presented here were used to estimate global species richness patterns which were: validated against previous findings whenever possible, peer-reviewed and published. However, please be aware that the individual species-level maps were not reviewed by independent experts and were mainly evaluated through common model skills metrics and visually examined by Fabio Benedetti. The species distribution models built for the study were designed to detect suitable environmental conditions based on the set of occurrences made available to the scientific community. As a result, some parts of the global ocean may show high habitat suitability values although the species modelled actually never occurs there due to a combination of complex biotic and abiotic factors that could not be integrated in the SDMs. We have greater confidence in the overall richness patterns than in the species maps due to various biases and assumptions made in the distribution modelling framework. Please use the species-level maps with caution and consider the limitations associated with outputs seeming from species distribution models.
- **Acknowledgements:** This publication has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862923 (project AtlantECO). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 845
- **File size:** 15 MB/file = total 12.7 GB

- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 50,700 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 845 [species]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [presence probability (0-1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation]
- **Time period(s):** 1 [contemporary (2012-2031)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface waters]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2012-2031)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 3 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Generalized Additive Models (GAM)
 - Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 9 predictors (see list of associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

ZOOBASE - Benedetti et al. (2021) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5101349>

[See list of taxa in Appendix 1](#)

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Dissolved oxygen concentration at 175m depth from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Calculated annual range of SST (dsST)
- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($N^* = [\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio
- Calculated excess of silicates to nitrates ($\text{Si}^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM)

Logarithmic values were used for Chlorophyll (logChl).

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Benedetti, F., Vogt, M., Elizondo, U.H., Righetti, D., Zimmermann, N.E. and Gruber, N., 2021. Major restructuring of marine plankton assemblages under global warming. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), p.5226, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x>.

Abstract: Marine phytoplankton and zooplankton form the basis of the ocean's food-web, yet the impacts of climate change on their biodiversity are poorly understood. Here, we use an ensemble of species distribution models for a total of 336 phytoplankton and 524 zooplankton species to determine their present and future habitat suitability patterns. For the end of this century, under a high emission scenario, we find an overall increase in plankton species richness driven by ocean warming, and a poleward shift of the species' distributions at a median speed of 35 km/decade. Phytoplankton species richness is projected to increase by more than 16% over most regions except for the Arctic Ocean. In contrast, zooplankton richness is projected to slightly decline in the tropics, but to increase strongly in temperate to subpolar latitudes. In these latitudes, nearly 40% of the phytoplankton and zooplankton assemblages are replaced by poleward shifting species. This implies that climate change threatens the contribution of plankton communities to plankton-mediated ecosystem services such as biological carbon sequestration.

4.2 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #2

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 326 species of autotrophs and 517 species of heterotrophs in the surface mixed layer, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary and future (2012-2100) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides contemporary and future projections of marine planktonic species ($n = 843$) based on the Habitat Suitability Index retrieved from an ensemble across Species Distribution Models accounting for several sources of uncertainty (algorithm complexity and climate models). Each species file can be opened and contains 5 dimensions (rcp, statistic, timesteps, latitude and longitude). The data covers the time period from 2012 until 2100 in monthly timesteps for three different RCPs (RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5). The maps cover the time period from 2012 until 2100 in monthly timesteps for three different RCPs (RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5). The statistics (mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum) are calculated across three different Earth System Models (CNRM-CM5, GFDL-ESM2M, IPSL-CM5A-LR) and three different algorithms (General Linear Model, General Additive Model and an Artificial Neural Network). The resolution of the data is 1° by 1° monthly resolution.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

not provided

Caption: not provided

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, presence, ocean microbiome, autotrophs, heterotrophs, phytoplankton, zooplankton, contemporary climate conditions, future climate projections
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** not provided
- **Acknowledgements:** This publication has received funding from the Geneva Science Policy Interface under contract number ##### (MAPMAKER), and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862923 (project AtlantECO). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 74,184
- **File size:** 14.8 MB/file = total 1.1 TB
- **File format:** zarr file storage system (<https://zarr.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>)(*zarr)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 13,353,120 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 843 [species]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [presence probability (0-1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation]
- **Time periods(s):** 88 years [2012-2100]
- **Climate scenario(s):** 3 [RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface mixed layer]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary and future (2012-2100)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 3 models
 - Generalized Additive Models (GAM)
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 19 predictors (see list of associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** ensemble of 3 Earth System Models (ESMs)
 - Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM-CM5)
 - Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model (GFDL-ESM2M)
 - Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace Climate Model 5A-Long Range (IPSL-CM5A-LR)

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

See the list of taxonomic entities (not provided) in Appendix 1

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of mixed-layer depth (MLD, m) based on the temperature criterion of [De Boyer-Montegut et al. \(2004\)](#) from the [Argo floats data](#)
- Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Surface wind stress (m s^{-1}) from the [Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform Atlas et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; μatm) from [Landschützer et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; atm) from the Surface Ocean CO_2 Atlas ([SOCATv2](#)); Bakker et al. (2014); Landschützer et al. (2014)
- Mean Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$) from the daily [satellite altimetry observations](#), following the method of Qiu & Chen (2011)
- Calculated PAR over the mixed layer depth (MLD) (MLPAR, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from Brun et al. (2015)
- Calculated annual range of SST (dSST)
- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($\text{N}^* = [\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio
- Calculated excess of silicates to nitrates ($\text{Si}^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM)

Logarithmic values were considered for skewed variables, i.e. $\log\text{NO}_3$, $\log\text{PO}_4$, $\log\text{SiOH}_4$, $\log\text{EKE}$, and $\log\text{Chl}$.

Associated References - Software/Code

MAPMAKER: A PlotlyApp to serve biodiversity data from species distribution modelling to policymakers <https://mapmaker-new.ethz.ch/>

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Dominic Eriksson (in preparation)

Xinhang Li, MSc thesis, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000652200>.

Abstract: Marine plankton are at the base of the marine food webs. They perform essential ecological functions such as biological carbon sequestration and food provision to higher trophic levels. However, they are subject to anthropogenic climate change, and the impacts of different climate change scenarios on marine plankton biodiversity and habitat are poorly quantified. In this study, we use an ensemble of species distribution models to project habitat suitability index for a total of 843 marine plankton species (326 phytoplankton and 517 zooplankton) under three climate change scenarios (RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) from 2012-2100. The differences in plankton biodiversity among the three RCPs are substantial. In RCP2.6, compared to the baseline (2012-2031), the global mean relative increase in plankton species richness by the end of the 21st century (2081-2100) is only 1.6%. This relative change increases to 3.4% in RCP4.5 and further to 8.0% in RCP8.5. From RCP2.6 to RCP8.5, there is a remarkable expansion of species richness change hotspots. In RCP8.5, the species richness change hotspots will cover three fourths of the global surface ocean from 60°N to 60°S by the end of the 21st century. The majority of plankton species (85%) will shift poleward in the future in response to ocean warming. Furthermore, there is a significant acceleration of poleward shift,

from 3.76 km/dec in RCP2.6 to 19.95 km/dec in RCP8.5. The Arctic Ocean is the ocean basin that will experience the highest level of species turnover in plankton assemblages under all RCP scenarios, which indicates a high sensitivity to climate change in this region. Species turnover in the Arctic Ocean amounts to 0.45 in RCP8.5, which means that nearly half of the species in plankton assemblages will be replaced by the end of the 21st century. Phytoplankton and zooplankton are different in their biodiversity responses to ocean warming in the tropics: Phytoplankton species richness will increase under all RCP scenarios, by contrast, zooplankton species richness will slightly decrease in RCP8.5, and slightly increase in RCP4.5 and RCP2.6. Additionally, the dissimilarity of phytoplankton assemblage composition between baseline and future is driven by both turnover and nestedness, whereas the dissimilarity of zooplankton assemblage composition between baseline and future is primarily driven by species turnover. Overall, limiting global warming below 1.5°C can avoid the significant expansion of plankton richness change hotspots under RCP8.5 compared to RCP2.6, constrain the speed of poleward habitat shift below one fifth of that in RCP8.5, and keep the species turnover in the Arctic Ocean at about half of that in RCP8.5. Potential negative impacts on ocean carbon cycles and ecosystem services caused by marine plankton biodiversity change and habitat shift can be avoided if collaborative efforts are made to limit global warming below 1.5 °C.

4.3 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #3

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 14 species of nitrogen-fixing taxa (diazotrophs) in epipelagic waters (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides monthly global biogeography of 14 diazotroph species including cyanobacterial and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs. Each netCDF file contains the ensemble average, standard deviation, maximum and minimum across all ensemble members. We used total, group-specific and cruise-specific target group approaches.

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Species or genus-level spatial distribution of diazotrophs computed as the time-averaged habitat suitability per taxon per area across 12 months and 90 ensemble members. Each taxon was modeled separately for each month on a 1° longitude 1° latitude spatial resolution. Red points indicate the gridded presences that were available for the modeling pipeline. Figure S10 of Eriksson et al. 2023)

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, presence, ocean microbiome, autotrophs, diazotrophs, nitrogen-fixers, contemporary climate conditions
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** not provided
- **Acknowledgements:** This publication has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059915 (project BIOcean5D) and No 862923 (project AtlantECO). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 14
- **File size:** 12 MB/file = total 168 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 672 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 14 [species]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [presence probability (0-1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 4 [mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum]
- **Time period(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic waters (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2012)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 3 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Generalized Additive Models (GAM)
 - Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 16 predictors (see list and associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

Data set available here: <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000635803>

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- (dark green) Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; www.gbif.org, last access: 20 October 2021)
- (blue) J. J. Pierella Karlusich, E. Pelletier, F. Lombard, M. Carsique, E. Dvorak, S. Colin, M. Picheral, F. M. Cornejo-Castillo, S. G. Acinas, R. Pepperkok, E. Karsenti, C. de Vargas, P. Wincker, C. Bowler, R. A. Foster, Global distribution patterns of marine nitrogen-fixers by imaging and molecular methods. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 4160 (2021).
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- (red) Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS; www.obis.org/, last access: 21 October 2021)
- (dark blue) W. Tang, N. Cassar, Data-driven modeling of the distribution of diazotrophs in the global ocean. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 46, 12258–12269 (2019).

[See list of taxonomic entities in Appendix 1](#)

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of mixed-layer depth (MLD, m) based on the temperature criterion of [De Boyer-Montégut et al. \(2004\)](#) from the [Argo floats data](#)
- Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Surface wind stress (m s^{-1}) from the [Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform Atlas et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; μatm) from [Landschützer et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; atm) from the Surface Ocean CO_2 Atlas ([SOCATv2](#)); Bakker et al. (2014); Landschützer et al. (2014)
- Mean Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$) from the daily [satellite altimetry observations](#), following the method of Qiu & Chen (2011)
- Calculated PAR over the mixed layer depth (MLD) (MLPAR, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from Brun et al. (2015)
- Calculated annual range of SST (dSST)

- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($N^* = [\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio
- Calculated excess of silicates to nitrates ($Si^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM)

Logarithmic values were considered for skewed variables, i.e. $\log\text{NO}_3$, $\log\text{PO}_4$, $\log\text{SiOH}_4$, $\log\text{EKE}$, and $\log\text{Chl}$.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Eriksson, D., Righetti, D., Gruber, G., Benedetti, F., Paoli, L., Salazar, G., Sunagawa, S., Vogt, M., Nitrogen fixation rates increase with diazotroph richness in the global ocean, 2023. *EcoEvoRxiv*, <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2Z323>.

Abstract: Marine diazotrophs, a highly specialized group of marine prokaryotes, convert atmospheric nitrogen gas into bioavailable forms of nitrogen and are thus critical to maintain the fertility of the ocean. However, little is known about the link between global-scale diazotroph diversity and marine N_2 fixation rates. Here, we address this question by integrating DNA sequencing and microscopy-based observations for a total of 14 species into species distribution models to overcome data sparsity and uneven sampling efforts. Our study compiles diazotroph occurrences with more than 22 thousand observations and we identify distinct biogeographic patterns for the major known taxa of diazotrophs, including colony forming, unicellular, symbiotic, and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs. Non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs show higher habitat suitability in upwelling regions compared to their cyanobacterial relatives. A strong latitudinal gradient in diazotrophic richness emerges from these biogeographic patterns, with richness being highest in tropical and subtropical regions and declining towards the poles. Temperature and nutrient-related environmental parameters rank as the most important predictors of the biogeography explaining up to 36% of the variance for specific taxa. We find diazotroph richness to be positively correlated with nitrogen fixation rates, suggesting efficient resource partitioning rather than competitive exclusion as the dominant driver of the observed biodiversity patterns. Our work reveals that important biodiversity-ecosystem-function relationships associated with global biogeochemical cycling exist in marine plankton ecosystems, and suggests that global nitrogen fixation rates and diazotroph diversity are likely to increase in a warming ocean.

4.4 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #4

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 374 Single-cell and Metagenome Assembled Genomes (SMAGs) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides the projected presence probabilities of 374 Single-cell and Metagenome Assembled Genomes (SMAGs) from Delmont et al. (2022). They are projected using 10 year average ensemble climatologies (CMIP5) in the present day (2006-15) and in the future (2090-99, RCP8.5).

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: World map distribution projections for three eukaryotic MAGs during the periods of 2006–15 and 2090–99. (Figure 4 of Delmont et al. 2022)

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, presence, ocean microbiome, single-cell and metagenome assembled genomes (SMAGs), contemporary climate conditions, future climate projections
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 748
- **File size:** 2.04 MB/file = total 1.53 GB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 9,646 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 374 [SMAGS]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [presence probability (0-1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 1 [mean]
- **Time periods(s):** 2 [present day (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [time period average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2012-2031) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 4 models
 - Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)
 - Random Forest (RF)
 - Neural Networks (NN)
 - General Additive Models (GAM)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 7 predictors (see list and associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** ensemble of 6 Earth System Models
 - CESM1-BGC (Gent et al., 2011)
 - GFDL-ESM2G & GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013)
 - HadGEM2-ES (Collins et al., 2011)
 - IPSL-CM5A-LR & IPSL-CM5A-MR (Dufresne et al., 2013)
 - MPI-ESM-LR & MPI-ESM-MR (Giorgetta et al., 2013)
 - NorESM1-ME (Bentsen et al., 2013)

Associated References - Microbiome observations

- Raw genomic data: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100123>
- Processed data: <https://www.genoscope.cns.fr/tara/>
- Data for Agnostos analyses: https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Delmont_et_al_2022/19403531
- Genome statistics and taxonomical inferences are provided in Table S3 of Delmont et al. (2022): <https://www.cell.com/cms/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100123/attachment/3e9b36db-f233-4708-b5b2-14694d86064d/mmc5.xlsx>

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- climatological dissolved iron (Fe) the biogeochemical model PISCES-v2 (Aumont et al. 2015)
- a seasonality index of nitrate (SI NO_3). SI NO_3 is defined as the range of nitrate concentrations over the year in one grid cell divided by the maximum range encountered in WOA13 at the *Tara* Oceans sampling stations.

Associated References - Software/Code

- Anvi'o pipeline (Eren et al. 2021): <https://anvio.org/>
- Agnostos pipeline (Vanni et al., 2021): <https://github.com/functional-dark-side/agnostos-wf>

- Custom codes required to perform analyses related to Agnostos (Delmont et al. 2022): <https://zenodo.org/record/6379623>

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Delmont, T., Gaia, M., Hinsinger, D., Frémont, P., Vanni, C., Fernandez-Guerra, A., Eren, A. M., Kourlaiev, A., d'Agata, L., Clayssen, Q., Villar, E., Labadie, K., Cruaud, C., Poulain, J., Da Silva, C., Wessner, M., Noel, B., Aury, J-M., Sunagawa, S., Acinas, S., Bork, P., Karsenti, E., Bowler, C., Sardet, C., Stemmann, L., de Vargas, C., Wincker, P., Lescot, M., Babin, M., Gorsky, G., Grimsley, N., Guidi, L., Hingamp, P., Jaillon, O., Kandels, S., Iudicone, D., Ogata, H., Pesant, S., Sullivan, M., Not, F., Karp-Boss, L., Boss, E., Cochrane, G., Follows, M., Poulton, N., Raes, J., Sieracki, M., Speich, S., de Vargas, Bowler, C., Karsenti, E., Pelletier, P., Wincker, P., Jaillon, O.. Functional repertoire convergence of distantly related eukaryotic plankton lineages abundant in the sunlit ocean, *Cell Genomics*, Volume 2, Issue 5, 2022, 100123, ISSN 2666-979X, [doi: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100123](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100123).

Abstract: Marine planktonic eukaryotes play critical roles in global biogeochemical cycles and climate. However, their poor representation in culture collections limits our understanding of the evolutionary history and genomic underpinnings of planktonic ecosystems. Here, we used 280 billion *Tara* Oceans metagenomic reads from polar, temperate, and tropical sunlit oceans to reconstruct and manually curate more than 700 abundant and widespread eukaryotic environmental genomes ranging from 10 Mbp to 1.3 Gbp. This genomic resource covers a wide range of poorly characterized eukaryotic lineages that complement long-standing contributions from culture collections while better representing plankton in the upper layer of the oceans. We performed the first, to our knowledge, comprehensive genome-wide functional classification of abundant unicellular eukaryotic plankton, revealing four major groups connecting distantly related lineages. Neither trophic modes of plankton nor its vertical evolutionary history could completely explain the functional repertoire convergence of major eukaryotic lineages that coexisted within oceanic currents for millions of years.

4.5 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #5

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 53 Operational Taxonomic Units of the phylum Picozoa (pOTUs) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides global projections of habitat suitability index (HSI) estimated for each of 53 different picozoa operational taxonomic units (pOTUs), as described in Huber et al. 2024. For each pOTU-level map, mean, max, min, stdev, and coefficient of variation of HSI values computed across several algorithms are provided. We developed the single pOTU HSI maps from 2,394 eDNA samples relative to the pico-size fraction (i.e. 0.2 to 5 μ m), which were retrieved from the EukBank database. Picozoa samples were classified based on their depth into epipelagic (0-200 m), mesopelagic (200-1000 m) and bathypelagic (>1000 m) samples. To estimate the HSI, we used species distribution models based on a presence/absence design; among all retrieved samples of pico-eukaryotes, georeferenced samples where a specific pOTU was detected were treated as presences, while sampling locations where that pOTU was not detected were treated as (pseudo-) absences. For each pOTU, we contrasted average multi-year depth-specific environmental conditions at presence vs absence points using an ensemble of modelling algorithms, including Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) and Random Forest (RF). Models were calibrated using multi-year average conditions across epipelagic, mesopelagic and bathypelagic layers. HSI maps were projected over epipelagic conditions only, due to lack of sufficient data coverage for deeper layers. Environmental predictors were retrieved from the World Ocean Atlas 2018.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Global annual habitat suitability index (HSI) of 53 abundant pOTUs in the epipelagic layer (0-200m), grouped by three categories based on observed abundance patterns: widespread (green), polar (cyan), non-polar (red). For more details see Huber et al. 2024 (accepted manuscript). Figure 9 from Huber et al. (2024)

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Additional information

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- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, presence, ocean microbiome, picozoa operational taxonomic units (pOTUs), contemporary climate conditions
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** not provided
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 53
- **File size:** 1.3 MB/file = total 66 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 265 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 53 [pOTUs]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [presence probability (0-1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 5 [minimum, maximum, average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation]
- **Time period(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [multi-year average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2017)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 4 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Artificial Neural Network (ANN)
 - Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)
 - Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 8 predictors (see list and associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

AtlantECO-BASE genomic data collections:

- https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/BASE/omics_18S/

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Temperature (°C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Mixed-layer depth (m) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Salinity from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- dissolved oxygen ($\mu\text{M} \times \text{kg}^{-10}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Conductivity from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Phosphate concentration ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Nitrate ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) ([WOA18/DATA](#)) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Excess of nitrates relative to the Redfield ratio of 16:1 (μM), computed as $[\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$.

Associated References - Software/Code

https://github.com/hubermmp/picozoa_distribution

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Huber, P., D., De Angelis, H., Sarmiento, S., Metz, C. R., Giner, C., de Vargas, L., Maiorano, R., Massana, R. Logares. 2024. Global Distribution, Diversity, and Ecological Niche of Picozoa, a widespread and enigmatic marine protist lineage. *Microbiome*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-024-01874-1>

Abstract: The backbone of the eukaryotic tree of life contains taxa only found in molecular surveys, of which we still have a limited understanding. Such is the case of Picozoa, an enigmatic lineage of heterotrophic picoeukaryotes placed within Archaeplastida, a supergroup composed of photosynthetic organisms. Here we present an assessment of the diversity, distribution, and ecology of Picozoa by analyzing the EukBank

amplicon database. This dataset includes ~12 800 georeferenced freshwater, soil, and marine samples in which the eukaryotic diversity has been studied by 18S V4 rRNA gene sequencing. Picozoa was among the ten most abundant eukaryotic groups, found almost exclusively in marine environments. The phylum was represented by 179 Picozoa's OTU (pOTUs) placed in five phylogenetic clades. Picozoa community structure had a clear latitudinal pattern, with polar assemblages tending to cluster separately from non-polar ones. Based on the abundance and occupancy pattern, the pOTUs were classified into four categories: Low-abundant (122 pOTUs), Widespread (8 pOTUs), Polar (16 pOTUs), and Non-polar (29 pOTUs). We calculated the ecological niche of the abundant categories. Notably, pOTUs sharing similar ecological niches were not closely related species, indicating a phylogenetic overdispersion in Picozoa communities. This could be attributed to competitive exclusion and the strong influence of the seasonal amplitude of variations in environmental factors, such as temperature, shaping physiological and ecological traits. Overall, this study contributes to advancing our understanding of the evolutionary dynamics and ecological strategies of uncharted protists.

4.6 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #6

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Abundance of 17 groups of autotrophs in the surface mixed layer, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides a global ensemble modeling framework allying cell abundance dataset derived from empirical quantification of phytoplankton groups in metagenomic samples with global environmental variables. Cell abundances of phytoplankton groups were estimated from the quantification of the psbO-gene in metagenomics samples from the Tara Oceans and Tara Pacific expeditions. Phytoplankton communities were resolved into 16 taxonomic groups. Separate models were trained for each of 17 responses (16 groups + total phytoplankton), using only samples with complete predictors and targets. Hyperparameters (tree number, minimum leaf size) were tuned by Bayesian optimization. Optimal configurations were determined via 5-fold cross-validation, balancing predictive accuracy and data use. Performance was quantified using RMSE and R^2 . Final models were retrained with all valid data and applied to the global prediction grid. The ensemble models relied on a suite of key environmental predictors, sea surface temperature (SST), sea surface salinity (SSS), chlorophyll-a, iron, nitrate, phosphate, and silicate. Model predictions were made over monthly global environmental grids, with phytoplankton maps generated at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution. We computed Mahalanobis distances between environmental conditions at each grid point and the training dataset to identify regions outside the empirical environmental envelope and quantify prediction confidence and extrapolation risk. In parallel, we conducted sensitivity analyses by varying subsets of the data, quantifying how training data composition influences global predictions.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Modeled distribution and latitudinal variation of phytoplankton cell abundance and composition. (Left) Global map of total phytoplankton cell concentration (\log_{10} cells L^{-1}). (Center) Latitudinal composition (% abundance) of major phytoplankton groups, showing relative dominance across latitude bands. (Right) Latitudinal variation in absolute cell concentration (\log_{10} cells L^{-1}) for each group, with the dashed line indicating total modeled cell concentration. Colors represent functional groups: Diatoms, Other photosynthetic prokaryotes, Prochlorococcus, Chlorophyta, Other Eukaryota, Synechococcus, and Unidentified. (Figure 6 from Crédeville et al. 2025)

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Additional information

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- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, presence, ocean microbiome, autotrophs, phytoplankton, contemporary climate conditions

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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 1
- **File size:** not provided
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 34 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 17 [16 clades and total]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [abundance (cells/L)]
- **Statistic(s):** 2 [mean, standard deviation]
- **Time periods(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [annual climatology]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface mixed layer]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2012)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** bagging regression trees ensemble models
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 7 predictors (see list below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

See [Crédeville et al. \(2025\)](#) for details.

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Dissolved iron (Fe) from the biogeochemical model PISCES-v2 (Aumont et al. 2015)

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Margaux Crédeville, Roy El Hourany, Swan L. S. Sow, Julie Poulain, Manon Depaty, Eric Pelletier, Zoé Mériguet, Marie-Fanny Racault, Genoscope Sequencing Team, Aude Perdereau, Laurie Bertrand, Frédérick Gavory,

Priscillia Gourvil, Céline Orvain, Morgane Ratin, Laurence Garczarek, Tom O Delmont, Adrien Thurotte, Corinne Le Quéré, Juan J Pierella Karlusich, Chris Bowler, Samuel Chaffron, Patrick Wincker, Fabien Lombard, Olivier Jaillon. 2025. Genomics-based quantitative biogeography of marine plankton. bioRxiv 2025.10.25.684415; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.10.25.684415>

Abstract: Marine plankton are key drivers of ocean productivity and global carbon cycling, yet their quantitative biogeography remains poorly characterized. Environmental genomic datasets are inherently compositional, restricting analyses to relative abundances and limiting their integration into ecological and biogeochemical models. Here we combine DNA mass measurements, filtered seawater volumes, and metagenomic relative abundances to generate absolute estimates of cell concentrations and carbon biomass of plankton across the global ocean. Leveraging thousands of samples collected during several Tara expeditions, this approach provides quantitative estimates for hundreds of eukaryotic and thousands of prokaryotic environmental genomes, unveiling ecological associations not captured by compositional data. Using the psbO marker gene, we reconstruct quantitative biogeographies of photosynthetic lineages and, through global-scale modeling, project their distributions to generate quantitative maps of phytoplankton communities across the world's ocean. By bridging genomic data with biogeochemical metrics, this study provides novel resources for integrating plankton at genomic resolution into next-generation biogeochemical models.

4.7 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #7

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Presence probability (0-1) of 20 Operational Protein Units (OPUs) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps is based on protein data from 1,379 metagenomes (from AtlantECO-BASEv2), we define Operational Protein Units (OPUs) through a sensitive heuristic clustering strategy that captures both known and unknown amino acid sequences, including those associated with "functional dark matter" often missed by traditional analyses. Based on abundance and occurrence, 20 representative OPUs were selected for the modelling process. These OPUs were assigned to different functional pathways. For each of 20 OPUs we ran species distribution models to predict their global distribution. We modeled using four models- Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Boosted Regression Trees (BRT), Random Forest (RF), resulting in 80 maps. With this, with the ensemble approach, we used the mean of the suitability among the four models, resulting in the potential distribution maps. The OPUs were modeled to sunlit ocean regions (< 200 meters). The models showed different OPUs distribution patterns: widely, polar, no polar, tropical, temperate and sub polar distributions. These resulting maps are stored in the folder "SDM OPUs". We used species distribution models to predict the global distribution of 20 OPUs well represented across all the ocean basins.

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Global annual habitat suitability index (HSI) for each OPUs distribution in the Global Ocean.

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- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, presence, ocean microbiome, operational protein units (OPUs), contemporary climate conditions
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 20
- **File size:** not provided
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 40 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 20 [OPUs]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [presence probability (0-1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 2 [average, coefficient of variation]
- **Time periods(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [multi-year average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]

- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2017)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 4 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Artificial Neural Network (ANN)
 - Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)
 - Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 8 predictors (see list and associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Temperature (°C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Mixed-layer depth (m) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Salinity from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- dissolved oxygen ($\mu\text{M} \times \text{kg}^{-10}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Conductivity from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Phosphate concentration ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Nitrate ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) ([WOA18/DATA](#)) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Excess of nitrates relative to the Redfield ratio of 16:1 (μM), computed as $[\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Huber et al. (in prep)

Abstract: Microbial communities are pivotal in driving global biogeochemical cycles, being essential for the health and functioning of marine ecosystems. While recent studies have explored their taxonomic and functional biogeography, the potential metabolisms underpinning biogeographical patterns in the ocean remain largely uncharted. In this study, we analyzed 1,379 metagenomes, using a sensitive heuristic clustering strategy to define Operational Protein Units (OPUs) from metagenomic protein datasets. These OPUs encompassed amino acid sequence information from both known and unknown taxa and metabolic functions, thereby capturing sequences often overlooked in previous taxonomic or metabolic pathway-based analyses—commonly referred to as "functional dark matter". Using these OPUs, we identified Ocean Microbiome Signatures (OMSs), functional groups that encapsulate the metabolic repertoire and ecological roles of marine microbial communities that we mapped across the global ocean. We identified ten distinct OMSs - each defined by unique functional traits, distribution patterns, and environmental associations - that collectively revealed the microbiome differences in substrate utilization, energy production strategies, and overall metabolic efficiency across oceanographic regions. Our findings provide a new framework for exploring the ecological roles of microbial metabolism in global ocean biogeochemical cycles. This approach moves beyond traditional metagenomic analyses focused solely on characterized metabolic pathways, offering a paradigm shift that integrates the vast, yet largely neglected, functional dark matter into our understanding of the ocean metabolism.

4.8 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #8

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Co-occurrence of 57,082 pairs of taxa in surface waters (10 m), projected under contemporary (2006-15) and future (2015-2100) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps is based on Association Distribution Modeling (ADM), which was conceived as a parallel to well-established Species Distribution Models, but dedicated to the modeling and prediction of pairwise ecological associations, statistical proxies for potential biotic interactions, with the aim of further modelling community biogeography with better reliability. Here, only co-occurrence projections are reported, with 3 possible states: 1 for co-presence of both species, 0 for co-absence, and -1 for exclusion (i.e., one species is present but not the other). On the one hand, 57,082 ADMs were projected in the contemporary era using the World Ocean Atlas 18 dataset (Boyer et al. 2018). On the other hand, 17,517 ADMs were projected throughout the century using IPSL (Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace) climate model under a Representation Concentration Pathway 4.5 climate scenario (Boucher et al. 2020).

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Schematic overview of the ADM conceptual framework in parallel with the SDM approach. The starting point involves observed counts (or abundances) of m species (or metagenomics assembled genomes) across n samples. After inputting data from

the World Ocean Atlas 18 climatologies as samples, species biogeography using SDMs or ecological associations between species using ADMs can be modelled and projected in space and time through WOA18 or IPSL climate model data. cSDMs predict species presence and absence, while rSDMs predict species abundance. Here, cADMs project species co-presence, co-absence and exclusion, revealing potential species interaction biogeographies, while rADMs estimate local statistical association strengths α , derived from decomposing the global statistical association strength ρ [3]. These estimates enable the inference of predicted statistical forces ρ^* at global or regional scales, as exemplified in the Atlantic Ocean region (lower right map). CLR: centered log ratio. In the uploaded maps, only cADMs (for classification ADMs) are reported (co-occurrence and not co-abundance). Figure 10 from Gaudin et al. (2024).

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
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- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, co-occurrence, ocean microbiome, plankton, contemporary climate conditions, future climate projections
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 2
- **File size:** 294 MB and 181 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 74,599 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 57,082 [pairwise species associations]*

- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [co-occurrence (1, 0, -1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 1 [value from 1 model]
- **Time periods(s):** 2 [contemporary (2006-2015) and future (2015-2100)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [multi-year average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface waters (10 m)]

*a subset of 17,517 pairwise species associations were mapped under future conditions

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2012-2031)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** 1 model
 - Random Forest (RF) (*used*)
 - Gradient Tree Boosting (GTB) (*tested but not used*)
 - Support Vector Machine (SVM) (*tested but not used*)
 - Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) (*tested but not used*)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 4 predictors (see list below)
- **Climate model(s):** IPSL RCP 4.5 projections: from 2015 to 2100

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Temperature (°C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Salinity from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Silicate concentration ($\mu\text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Nitrate ($\mu\text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) ([WOA18/DATA](#)) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))

Associated References - Software/Code

<https://gitlab.univ-nantes.fr/combi-ls2n/adm>

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Gaudin, M., Eveillard, D. & Chaffron, S. Ecological associations distribution modelling of marine plankton at a global scale. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* **379**, 20230169 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2023.0169>

Abstract: Marine plankton communities form intricate networks of interacting organisms at the base of the food chain, and play a central role in regulating ocean biogeochemical cycles and climate. However, predicting plankton community shifts in response to climate change remains challenging. While species distribution models are valuable tools for predicting changes in species biogeography under climate change scenarios, they generally overlook the key role of biotic interactions, which can significantly shape ecological processes and ecosystem responses. Here, we introduce a novel statistical framework, association distribution modelling (ADM), designed to model and predict ecological associations distribution in space and time. Applied on a Tara Oceans genome-resolved metagenomics dataset, the present-day biogeography of ADM-inferred marine plankton associations revealed four major biogeographic biomes organized along a latitudinal gradient. We predicted the evolution of these biome-specific communities in response to a climate change scenario, highlighting differential responses to environmental change. Finally, we explored the functional potential of impacted plankton communities, focusing on carbon fixation, outlining the predicted evolution of its geographical distribution and implications for ecosystem function.

4.9 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #9

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Species richness of autotrophs in the surface mixed layer, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012-2031) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 538 taxa including species of diatoms, dinoflagellates and coccolithophores.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides phytoplankton species richness estimated from the binarized (presence–absence transformed) habitat suitability patterns of 536 – 538 phytoplankton species including diatoms, dinoflagellates, coccolithophores, and a few minor groups. We used Total and group-specific target group approach

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Monthly mean climatological surface ocean phytoplankton diversity, adapted from Righetti et al. (2019). Colors indicate the simulated number of species present during any given month of the year.

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, species richness, ocean microbiome, phytoplankton, diatoms, dinoflagellates, coccolithophores, contemporary climate conditions
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 1
- **File size:** 3 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 12 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 1 [autotrophs]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [species richness]
- **Statistic(s):** 1 [ensemble mean]
- **Time periods(s):** 1 [contemporary (2012-2031)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface mixed layer]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2012-2031)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 3 models
 - Generalized Additive Models (GAM)
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)

- Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s)**: ensemble of 19 predictors (see list of associated references below)
- **Climate model(s)**: not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

- PHYTOBASE - Righetti et al. 2019 (<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2019-159>)
- Data were compiled from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; <https://www.gbif.org>, retrieved on 7 December 2015), the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS; <https://www.obis.org>, retrieved on 5 December 2015), Villar et al. (2015), and the MAREDAT initiative (Buitenhuis et al. 2013). The final dataset contained 1,056,363 presence observations from 1298 species and two genera.
- Richness was calculated from the modelled habitat suitability of 538 taxa including species of diatoms, dinoflagellates and coccolithophores

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of mixed-layer depth (MLD, m) based on the temperature criterion of [De Boyer-Montegut et al. \(2004\)](#) from the [Argo floats data](#)
- Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Surface wind stress (m s^{-1}) from the [Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform Atlas et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; μatm) from [Landschützer et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; atm) from the Surface Ocean CO_2 Atlas ([SOCATv2](#)); Bakker et al. (2014); Landschützer et al. (2014)
- Mean Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$) from the daily [satellite altimetry observations](#), following the method of Qiu & Chen (2011)
- Calculated PAR over the mixed layer depth (MLD) (MLPAR, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from Brun et al. (2015)
- Calculated annual range of SST (dSST)
- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($\text{N}^* = [\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio
- Calculated excess of silicates to nitrates ($\text{Si}^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM)

Logarithmic values were considered for skewed variables, i.e. $\log\text{NO}_3$, $\log\text{PO}_4$, $\log\text{SiOH}_4$, $\log\text{EKE}$, and $\log\text{Chl}$.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Righetti, D., Vogt, M., Gruber, N., Psomas, A. and Zimmermann, N.E., 2019. Global pattern of phytoplankton diversity driven by temperature and environmental variability. *Science Advances*, 5(5), p.eau6253, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aau6253>.

Abstract: Despite their importance to ocean productivity, global patterns of marine phytoplankton diversity remain poorly characterized. Although temperature is considered a key driver of general marine biodiversity,

its specific role in phytoplankton diversity has remained unclear. We determined monthly phytoplankton species richness by using niche modeling and >540,000 global phytoplankton observations to predict biogeographic patterns of 536 phytoplankton species. Consistent with metabolic theory, phytoplankton richness in the tropics is about three times that in higher latitudes, with temperature being the most important driver. However, below 19°C, richness is lower than expected, with ~8°–14°C waters (~35° to 60° latitude) showing the greatest divergence from theoretical predictions. Regions of reduced richness are characterized by maximal species turnover and environmental variability, suggesting that the latter reduces species richness directly, or through enhancing competitive exclusion. The nonmonotonic relationship between phytoplankton richness and temperature suggests unanticipated complexity in responses of marine biodiversity to ocean warming.

4.10 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #10

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Species richness of three taxonomic groups of autotrophs, and eleven taxonomic groups of heterotrophs in surface waters, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of species belonging to each taxonomic group.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides functional group-level global monthly fields of species richness (estimated through the sum of species-level HSI) for the contemporary and future time periods (i.e., folder labelled 'Groups_species_richness_Benedettietal.2021'). There are two NetCDF files per functional group, one for each time period: contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100). Each NetCDF file records the monthly: minimum (Min), maximum (Max), mean, median and the standard deviation (Stdev) of the species richness estimated for 14 different plankton functional groups (Amphipoda, Appendicularia, Calanoida, Chaetognatha, Coccolithophores, Diatoms, Dinoflagellates, Euphausiids, Foraminifera, Jellyfish, Oithonida, Poecilostomatoida, Pteropoda and Thaliacea). For each functional group, species richness was estimated as the sum of the HSI predicted for the species composing that functional group.

The species distribution models used to generate the maps relied on background data were based on a "group-specific target group approach". Projections were made using an ensemble of five Earth System Models from the MAREMIP project: the Community Earth System Model version 1 (CESM1, POP-BEC), the Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model with Modular Ocean Model version 4 (GFDL-ESM2M; MOM-TOPAZ), the Institut Pierre Simon Laplace Climate Model version 5A-LR (IPSL-CM5A-LR; NEMO-PISCES), the Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM- CM5; NEMO-PISCES) and the Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate version 5 (MIROC5; [MRI.COM](https://www.mri.com)-MEM).

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Spatial distribution of the mean annual species richness (expressed in % of species modelled per group) for a) Diatoms ($n = 163$), b) Dinoflagellates ($n = 157$), c) Coccolithophores ($n = 27$), d) Calanoida ($n = 221$), e) Oithonida ($n = 12$), f) Poecilostomatoida ($n = 41$), g) Euphausiids ($n = 51$), h) Jellyfish ($n = 69$), i) Salps ($n = 12$), j) Pteropods ($n = 19$), k) Chaetognatha ($n = 27$), l) Amphipods ($n = 20$), m) Appendicularians ($n = 6$), and n) Foraminifera ($n = 26$). Blank areas correspond to those grid cells where richness projections were not possible for more than six months due to missing values in the monthly environmental climatologies the models were projected on.

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, species richness, ocean microbiome, autotrophs, heterotrophs, phytoplankton, zooplankton, contemporary climate conditions, future climate projections
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** Individual species-level maps used to estimate global species richness were not reviewed by independent experts and were mainly evaluated through common model skills metrics and visually examined by Fabio Benedetti. The species distribution models used here were designed to detect suitable environmental conditions based on the set of occurrences made available to the scientific community. As a result, some parts of the global ocean may show high habitat suitability values although the species modelled actually never occurs there due to a combination of complex biotic and abiotic factors that could not be integrated in the SDMs. We have greater confidence in the overall richness patterns than in the species maps due to various biases and assumptions made in the distribution modelling framework. Please use the species-level maps with caution and consider the limitations associated with outputs seeming from species distribution models.
- **Acknowledgements:** This publication has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862923 (project AtlantECO). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 28
- **File size:** 14.9 MB/file = total 416 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 1,680 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 14 [functional groups of species]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [species richness]
- **Statistic(s):** 5 [minimum, maximum, mean, median and standard deviation]
- **Time periods(s):** 2 [contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface waters]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 3 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)

- Generalized Additive Model (GAM)
- Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 9 predictors (see list of associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** ensemble of 5 Earth System Models (ESMs) forced by RCP8.5 scenario
 - Community Earth System Model version 1 (CESM1, POP-BEC)
 - Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model with Modular Ocean Model version 4 (GFDL-ESM2M; MOM-TOPAZ)
 - Institut Pierre Simon Laplace Climate Model version 5A-LR (IPSL-CM5A-LR; NEMO-PISCES)
 - Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM- CM5; NEMO-PISCES)
 - Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate version 5 (MIROC5; MRI.COM-MEM)

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Richness was calculated from the modelled habitat suitability of species belonging to 14 plankton functional groups: Amphipoda, Appendicularia, Calanoida, Chaetognatha, Coccolithophores, Diatoms, Dinoflagellates, Euphausiids, Foraminifera, Jellyfish, Oithonida, Poecilostomatoida, Pteropoda and Thaliacea.

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Dissolved oxygen concentration at 175m depth from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Calculated annual range of SST (dSST)
- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($\text{N}^* = [\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio
- Calculated excess of silicates to nitrates ($\text{Si}^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM)

Logarithmic values were used for Chlorophyll (logChl).

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Benedetti, F., Gruber, N., and Vogt, M. 2023. Global gradients in species richness of marine plankton functional groups. *Journal of Plankton Research*, <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbad044>.

Abstract: Marine phytoplankton and zooplankton form the basis of the ocean's food-web, yet the impacts of climate change on their biodiversity are poorly understood. Here, we use an ensemble of species distribution models for a total of 336 phytoplankton and 524 zooplankton species to determine their present and future habitat suitability patterns. For the end of this century, under a high emission scenario, we find an overall increase in plankton species richness driven by ocean warming, and a poleward shift of the species' distributions at a median speed of 35 km/decade. Phytoplankton species richness is projected to increase by more than 16% over most regions except for the Arctic Ocean. In contrast, zooplankton richness is projected to slightly decline in the tropics, but to increase strongly in temperate to subpolar latitudes. In these latitudes, nearly 40% of the phytoplankton and zooplankton assemblages are replaced by poleward shifting species.

This implies that climate change threatens the contribution of plankton communities to plankton-mediated ecosystem services such as biological carbon sequestration.

4.11 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #11

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Species richness of nitrogen-fixing taxa (diazotrophs) in epipelagic waters (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 14 species of cyanobacterial and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides monthly global marine diazotroph ensemble richness estimates from binarized (presence-absence transformed) habitat suitability patterns of 14 diazotroph species including cyanobacterial and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs. We used a total, group-specific and cruise-specific target group approach.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Figure 7: Global annual ensemble mean of diazotroph species richness based on presence-absence converted species distribution modelling outputs including a total of 15 taxa. White stipples indicate areas where the coefficient of variation between ensemble members was above the 70th percentile marking greater differences between model projections (from Eriksson et al., submitted).

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, species richness, ocean microbiome, nitrogen-fixers, diazotrophs, cyanobacteria, non-cyanobacteria, contemporary climate conditions
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** not provided
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 1
- **File size:** 12 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 48 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 1 [nitrogen-fixing taxa (diazotrophs)]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [species richness]
- **Statistic(s):** 4 [minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation]

- **Time period(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic waters (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2012)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 3 models
 - Generalized Additive Models (GAM)
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 16 predictors (see list and associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Species richness is based on the modelled habitat suitability of 14 species of cyanobacterial and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs:

- Gamma.A
- HBD-02
- HBD-03
- HBD-04
- HBD-05
- HBD-06
- *Richelia_intracellularis*
- *Trichodesmium_erythraeum*
- *Trichodesmium_thiebautii*
- UCYN.A1
- UCYN.A2
- UCYN.A
- UCYN.B
- UCYN.C

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- ; μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} ; μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$; μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of mixed-layer depth (MLD, m) based on the temperature criterion of [De Boyer-Montegut et al. \(2004\)](#) from the [Argo floats data](#)
- Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Surface wind stress (m s^{-1}) from the [Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform Atlas et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; μatm) from [Landschützer et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; atm) from the Surface Ocean CO_2 Atlas ([SOCATv2](#)); Bakker et al. (2014); Landschützer et al. (2014)

- Mean Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$) from the daily [satellite altimetry observations](#), following the method of Qiu & Chen (2011)
- Calculated PAR over the mixed layer depth (MLD) (MLPAR, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from Brun et al. (2015)
- Calculated annual range of SST (dSST)
- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($N^* = [\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio
- Calculated excess of silicates to nitrates ($Si^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM)

Logarithmic values were considered for skewed variables, i.e. logNO3, logPO4, logSiOH4, logEKE, and logChl.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Eriksson, D., Righetti, D., Gruber, G., Benedetti, F., Paoli, L., Salazar, G., Sunagawa, S., Vogt, M., Nitrogen fixation rates increase with diazotroph richness in the global ocean, 2023. EcoEvoRxiv, <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2Z323>.

Abstract: Marine diazotrophs, a highly specialized group of marine prokaryotes, convert atmospheric nitrogen gas into bioavailable forms of nitrogen and are thus critical to maintain the fertility of the ocean. However, little is known about the link between global-scale diazotroph diversity and marine N_2 fixation rates. Here, we address this question by integrating DNA sequencing and microscopy-based observations for a total of 14 species into species distribution models to overcome data sparsity and uneven sampling efforts. Our study compiles diazotroph occurrences with more than 22'000 thousand observations and we identify distinct biogeographic patterns for the major known taxa of diazotrophs, including colony forming, unicellular, symbiotic, and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs. Non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs show higher habitat suitability in upwelling regions compared to their cyanobacterial relatives. A strong latitudinal gradient in diazotrophic richness emerges from these biogeographic patterns, with richness being highest in tropical and subtropical regions and declining towards the poles. Temperature and nutrient-related environmental parameters rank as the most important predictors of the biogeography explaining up to 36% of the variance for specific taxa. We find diazotroph richness to be positively correlated with nitrogen fixation rates, suggesting efficient resource partitioning rather than competitive exclusion as the dominant driver of the observed biodiversity patterns. Our work reveals that important biodiversity-ecosystem-function relationships associated with global biogeochemical cycling exist in marine plankton ecosystems, and suggests that global nitrogen fixation rates and diazotroph diversity are likely to increase in a warming ocean.

4.12 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #12

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Richness of the phylum Picozoa in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 53 Operational Taxonomic Units of the phylum Picozoa (pOTUs).

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides global picozoa richness for the epipelagic layer, obtained as the sum of mean pOTU-level HSI values across all 53 pOTUs, and the coefficient of variation over all pOTUs-level HSI maps.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

not provided

Caption: not provided

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, species richness, ocean microbiome, picozoa operational taxonomic units (pOTUs), contemporary climate conditions
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 1
- **File size:** 0.52 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 5 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 1 [Picozoa]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [species richness]
- **Statistic(s):** 5 [minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation]
- **Time periods(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [multi-year average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2017)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 4 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Artificial Neural Network (ANN)
 - Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)
 - Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 9 predictors (see list below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

*models were calibrated across the 0-5 and 500 depth range

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Species richness is based on the modelled habitat suitability of 53 Operational Taxonomic Units of the phylum Picozoa (pOTUs)

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Temperature (°C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Mixed-layer depth (m) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Salinity from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Dissolved oxygen ($\mu\text{M} \times \text{kg}^{-10}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Conductivity from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Phosphate concentration ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Nitrate ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Excess of nitrates relative to the Redfield ratio of 16:1 (μM), computed as $[\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$.

Data were obtained with

- 1x1 degree horizontal grid
- 0-5,500 m depth range
- yearly temporal resolution. Temporal coverage was from 2005 to 2017 for mixed-layer depth, salinity, temperature and all available years for oxygen, nitrates and phosphates

Associated References - Software/Code

https://github.com/hubermp/picozoa_distribution

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Huber, P., D., De Angelis, H., Sarmiento, S., Metz, C. R., Giner, C., de Vargas, L., Maiorano, R., Massana, R. Logares. 2024. Global Distribution, Diversity, and Ecological Niche of Picozoa, a widespread and enigmatic marine protist lineage. *Microbiome*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-024-01874-1>

Abstract: The backbone of the eukaryotic tree of life contains taxa only found in molecular surveys, of which we still have a limited understanding. Such is the case of Picozoa, an enigmatic lineage of heterotrophic picoeukaryotes placed within Archaeplastida, a supergroup composed of photosynthetic organisms. Here we present an assessment of the diversity, distribution, and ecology of Picozoa by analyzing the EukBank amplicon database. This dataset includes ~12 800 georeferenced freshwater, soil, and marine samples in which the eukaryotic diversity has been studied by 18S V4 rRNA gene sequencing. Picozoa was among the ten most abundant eukaryotic groups, found almost exclusively in marine environments. The phylum was represented by 179 Picozoa's OTU (pOTUs) placed in five phylogenetic clades. Picozoa community structure had a clear latitudinal pattern, with polar assemblages tending to cluster separately from non-polar ones. Based on the abundance and occupancy pattern, the pOTUs were classified into four categories: Low-abundant (122 pOTUs), Widespread (8 pOTUs), Polar (16 pOTUs), and Non-polar (29 pOTUs). We calculated the ecological niche of the abundant categories. Notably, pOTUs sharing similar ecological niches were not closely related species, indicating a phylogenetic overdispersion in Picozoa communities. This could be attributed to competitive exclusion and the strong influence of the seasonal amplitude of variations in environmental factors, such as temperature, shaping physiological and ecological traits. Overall, this study contributes to advancing our understanding of the evolutionary dynamics and ecological strategies of uncharted protists.

4.13 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #13

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Taxonomic and functional diversity of prokaryotes in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of 1,210 marker gene-based Operational Taxonomic Units of prokaryotes (mOTUs).

Abstract

This collection of global maps is based on metagenomic data collected during multiple oceanographic expeditions, including Tara Oceans, Malaspina, GO-SHIP, bioGEO TRACES, and OSD2014. Sample metadata, including geographic coordinates and sampling depth, were curated and merged with the environmental raster stack using bilinear extraction (`terra::extract`). Only samples with complete environmental metadata and valid coordinates were retained, and with samples from the 0.22-3 μm size fraction. The metagenomic data is from AtlantECO-BASEv2, a database developed within the AtlantECO project. All the metagenomic data were analyzed using the version 5.0 of MGnify's pipeline. Taxonomic profiles were generated by running mOTUs on MGnify. For each sample ($n = 1,210$), tables containing mOTUs taxonomic assignments were downloaded and compiled into a single table. Diversity was then calculated from this dataset using the Shannon and Simpson indices in R (`vegan` package). We conducted our analysis separately, using either data from all expeditions pooled together or using only GO-SHIP data, as this was the only dataset covering the latitudinal gradient. We focused on the sunlit zone due to its ecological relevance for primary production and microbial functional diversity. To predict Simpson and Shannon diversity across global marine expeditions, we applied a species distribution modeling (SDM) framework using four algorithms within R, using the package "h2o" (v3.42.0.2). All models were trained to predict Simpson or Shannon functional/taxonomic diversity based on a selected set of non-collinear environmental predictors: mixed layer depth (MLD), chlorophyll (Chl), salinity (Sal), silicate (Si), temperature (T), and the excess of nitrates over phosphates (N^*) according to Redfield ratio $[\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$. Models were trained on the final dataset using 5-fold cross-validation, for four algorithms (Artificial Neural Network, Random Forest, Generalized Linear Model, Gradient Boosting Machine). Predictions were projected using each trained model. Extracted predictions at sampling locations were compared against observed Simpson/Shannon diversity values using Pearson correlation, RMSE, and R^2 . An ensemble prediction was calculated as the pixelwise mean across the four models.

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Ensemble map for Taxonomic Shannon diversity index. Data from Tara Oceans, Malaspina, GO-SHIP, bioGEO TRACES, and OSD2014 expedition.

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Additional information

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- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, diversity, ocean microbiome, marker gene-based Operational Taxonomic Units of prokaryotes (mOTUs), prokaryotes, contemporary climate conditions
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File(s) specifications

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Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 4 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 1 [prokaryotes]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 4 [Shannon taxonomic diversity, Simpson taxonomic diversity, Shannon functional diversity; Simpson functional diversity]

- **Statistic(s):** 1 [mean]
- **Time period(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [multi-year average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2017)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 4 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Artificial Neural Network (ANN)
 - Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)
 - Random Forest (RF)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 6 predictors (see list below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

Taxonomic profiles were generated by running mOTUs on MGnify. For each sample (n = 1,210), tables containing mOTUs taxonomic assignments were downloaded and compiled into a single table.

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Mixed layer depth (MLD) ([WOA18](#))
- Chlorophyll (Chl) ([WOA18](#))
- Salinity (Sal) ([WOA18](#))
- Silicate (Si) ([WOA18](#))
- Temperature (T) ([WOA18](#))
- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($N^* = [NO_3^-] - 16[PO_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

De Angelis et al. (2025)

Abstract: not provided

4.14 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #14

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Taxonomic diversity of prokaryotes (bacteria and archaea) in the surface mixed layer, projected under contemporary (2005-2012) environmental conditions, based on the modelled habitat suitability of marker gene-based Operational Taxonomic Units of prokaryotes (mOTUs).

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides global marine prokaryotic diversity using a standardized ensemble pipeline that integrates metagenomic profiles with environmental predictors. Metagenomic samples from the Ocean Microbiomics Database were processed into domain- and class-level taxonomic profiles, and diversity indices (richness, Shannon, Chao1) were estimated from rarified mOTU counts. Multiple algorithms—Generalized Linear and Additive Models, Random Forests, Boosted Regression Trees, Support Vector Machines, and shallow neural networks—were trained and tuned using five-fold cross-validation. Models were evaluated using root mean square error and R^2 , with only well-performing models ($R^2 \geq 0.25$) retained. Ensemble predictions were derived as the mean across all successful models, while associated uncertainty was quantified as the standard deviation among them. The resulting dataset contains annual, global projections of domain- and class-level prokaryotic diversity indices (richness, Shannon, Chao1). Each netCDF file provides both the ensemble average and standard deviation, offering spatially explicit estimates alongside model-based uncertainty.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Modeled surface bacterial and archaeal richness pattern. Global maps of annual richness patterns of marine Bacteria (left panel), and Archaea (right panel) are visualized with ensemble-based projections layered onto a Pacific-centered world map. Maps show modeled monthly mean annual richness and areas of uncertainty (white stippling) defined as regions with coefficient of variation $> 20\%$ across ensemble members. The predictive power of the model is annotated with the R^2 value in red in the lower-left corner of each map. The white contour line highlights hotspots of diversity defined as regions above 75th percentile of modeled richness. Latitudinal gradients are shown for the global ocean with shadings indicating model uncertainty shown as standard deviation across ensemble members. Dashed red lines and annotation in the upper right corner indicate the maximum latitudinal median diversity.

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)

- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, diversity, ocean microbiome, prokaryotes, bacteria, archaea, contemporary climate conditions
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File(s) specifications

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- **File size:** not provided MB/file = total 302 MB
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Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 2 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** not provided [bacteria & archaea domains & classes]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 3 [taxonomic richness, Shannon diversity, chao1 diversity]
- **Statistic(s):** 2 [mean, standard deviation]
- **Time periods(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2012)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** not provided [annual]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface mixed layer]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2012)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 6 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Generalized Additive Models (GAM)
 - Random Forest (RF)
 - MLP
 - BRT
 - SVM
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 16 predictors (see list and associated references below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

Metagenomic samples from the Ocean Microbiomics Database (<https://omdb.microbiomics.io>) were processed into domain- and class-level taxonomic profiles, and diversity indices (richness, Shannon, Chao1) were estimated from rarified mOTU counts.

See list of domains & classes (not provided) in Appendix 1

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO₃⁻; µM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))

- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Monthly climatologies of mixed-layer depth (MLD, m) based on the temperature criterion of [De Boyer-Montegut et al. \(2004\)](#) from the [Argo floats data](#)
- Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Monthly climatologies of chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Surface wind stress (m s^{-1}) from the [Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform Atlas et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; μatm) from [Landschützer et al. \(2011\)](#)
- Sea surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; atm) from the Surface Ocean CO_2 Atlas ([SOCATv2](#)); Bakker et al. (2014); Landschützer et al. (2014)
- Mean Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$) from the daily [satellite altimetry observations](#), following the method of Qiu & Chen (2011)
- Calculated PAR over the mixed layer depth (MLD) (MLPAR, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) from Brun et al. (2015)
- Calculated annual range of SST (dSST)
- Calculated excess of nitrate over phosphate ($\text{N}^* = [\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio
- Calculated excess of silicate over nitrate ($\text{Si}^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM) relative to the Redfield ratio

Logarithmic values were considered for skewed variables, i.e. $\log\text{NO}_3$, $\log\text{PO}_4$, $\log\text{SiOH}_4$, $\log\text{EKE}$, and $\log\text{Chl}$.

Associated References - Software/Code

- The code used to conduct the analyses presented in this work, are available at https://github.com/grp-bork/LDG_Eriksson_Schiller_2025.
- The code used to implement the habitat modeling pipeline is openly available at <https://github.com/alexschickele/CEPHALOPOD/>.

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Dominic Eriksson, Jonas Schiller, Alexandre Schickele, Taylor Priest, Anna Mankowski, Enzo Faucher, Lucas J. Ustick, Michael Kuhn, Samuel Miravet-Verde, Hans-Joachim Ruscheweyh, Corentin Clerc, Nicolas Gruber, Shinichi Sunagawa, Peer Bork, Meike Vogt. (2025) Variations in the latitudinal diversity gradients of the ocean microbiome, bioRxiv <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.10.13.682024>

Abstract: Latitudinal diversity gradients (LDGs), typically declining from equator to poles, are a pervasive macroecological pattern, yet their generality and drivers in the ocean microbiome remain widely unresolved. We integrated global-scale metagenomic data with habitat modeling to study marine microbial LDGs across seasons and depths. Surface mixed layer microbiomes exhibited diversity peaks at (sub)tropical latitudes and a poleward decline, whereas mesopelagic communities (200–1,000 m) showed no latitudinal diversity structuring. Taxonomic resolution revealed that the mixed layer LDG was underpinned by Alphaproteobacteria and Cyanobacteria, while other taxa exhibited distinct or contrasting LDGs. Diversity structuring also varied by seasons and regions, governed by temperature and nutrient availability. Together, these findings highlight that within the ocean microbiome, LDGs are not universal, but lineage-specific ecological strategies and responses to environmental gradients. Our study provides fundamental insights into the structuring of ocean microbiome diversity and lays the foundation for predicting responses to environmental change.

4.15 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #15

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Taxonomic and functional diversity of copepods in surface waters (0-10 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2012–2031) and future, end-of-century (2081–2100) environmental conditions, based on habitat suitability modelling of species-level functional traits for > 300 copepod species.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides global gridded estimates of the functional diversity (FD) of marine copepod assemblages. FD indices were estimated by combining species distribution models (SDMs) with species-level functional traits (i.e., body size, trophic group, feeding mode, myelination and spawning mode) for > 300 copepod species. The dataset includes two complementary products: a contemporary baseline representing average copepod FD patterns for the present-day ocean and a future projection representing expected end-of-century (2081–2100) average changes in FD under a high-emission climate scenario (RCP8.5). Both products are provided as monthly climatologies at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution for the surface ocean (0–10 m). Multiple FD indices were computed to cover multiple aspects of functional diversity including: functional richness, evenness, divergence, dispersion, and trait dissimilarity. These data allow researchers to investigate how copepod trait composition is structured across the global ocean today, and how it may be reshuffled in response to anthropogenic climate change. This dataset offers a valuable resource to assess potential impacts of changing zooplankton communities on marine productivity, carbon cycling, and climate feedbacks.

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Distribution of contemporary mean annual (a) species richness, (b) Faith index (Faith, functional richness), (c) standardized effect sizes (SES) of Faith, (d) functional evenness (FEve), (e) functional dispersion (FDis), and (f) functional divergence (FDiv). Faith estimates functional richness. SES Faith measures the difference between observed Faith and null Faith estimates obtained from a randomly assembled community of the species' same richness. Species richness and Faith were calculated on presence–absence data whereas FEve, FDis, and FDiv were weighed by habitat suitability indices ranging between 0 and 1 to better represent the distribution of habitat suitability in functional space.

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, diversity, ocean microbiome, heterotrophs, zooplankton, copepods, contemporary climate conditions, future climate projections
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 2
- **File size:** 136.7 MB/file = total 273.4 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 1,080 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 2 [copepod species & copepod functional traits]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 9 [Species richness, functional richness, standardized effect size of functional richness, functional dispersion, functional divergence, functional evenness, trait dissimilarity, trait turnover and trait nestedness]
- **Statistic(s):** 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation]
- **Time period(s):** 2 [contemporary (2012-2031) & end of century (2081-2100)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)] WGS84 reference system
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface waters (0-10 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2012-2031) & future, end-of-century (2081-2100)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 3 models
 - Generalized Linear Models (GLM)
 - Generalized Additive Models (GAM)
 - Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 6 predictors (see list below)
- **Climate model(s):** ensemble of 5 Earth System Models (ESMs) forced by RCP8.5 scenario
 - Community Earth System Model version 1 (CESM1, POP-BEC)
 - Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model with Modular Ocean Model version 4 (GFDL-ESM2M; MOM-TOPAZ)
 - Institut Pierre Simon Laplace Climate Model version 5A-LR (IPSL-CM5A-LR; NEMO-PISCES)
 - Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM- CM5; NEMO-PISCES)
 - Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate version 5 (MIROC5; MRI.COM-MEM)

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Associated References - Environmental predictors

A fixed set of predictors was applied to all models (chosen for low collinearity, global coverage, and relevance to copepod ecology).

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface Nitrate concentration (log-transformed) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface Photosynthetically Available Radiation (PAR) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface chlorophyll-a concentration from [SeaWiFS](#)
- Calculated surface excess (Redfield-based anomaly) in nitrate relative to phosphate (N*)
- Calculated surface excess (Redfield-based anomaly) in silicate relative to nitrate (Si*)

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Benedetti, F., Wydler, J., Clerc, C., Knecht, N. and Vogt, M. (2025), Emergent Relationships Between the Functional Diversity of Marine Planktonic Copepods and Ecosystem Functioning in the Global Ocean. *Glob Change Biol*, 31: e70094. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.70094>

Abstract: Copepods are a major group of the mesozooplankton and thus a key part of marine ecosystems worldwide. Their fitness and life strategies are determined by their functional traits which allow different species to exploit various ecological niches. The range of functional traits expressed in a community defines its functional diversity (FD), which can be used to investigate how communities utilize resources and shape ecosystem processes. However, the spatial patterns of copepod FD and their relation to ecosystem functioning remain poorly understood on a global scale. Here, we use estimates of copepod community composition derived from species distribution models in combination with functional traits and indicators of ecosystem functioning to investigate the distribution of multiple facets of copepod FD, their relationships with species richness and ecosystem processes. We also project how anthropogenic climate change will impact the facets of copepod FD. We find that the facets of FD respond to species richness with variable strength and directions: functional richness, divergence, and dispersion increase with species richness whereas functional evenness and trait dissimilarity decrease. We find that primary production, mesozooplankton biomass and carbon export efficiency decrease with species richness, functional richness, divergence and dispersion. This suggests that ecosystem functioning may be disproportionately influenced by the traits of a few dominant species in line with the mass ratio hypothesis. Furthermore, climate change is projected to promote trait homogenization globally, which may decrease mesozooplankton biomass and carbon export efficiency globally. The emergent covariance patterns between copepod FD and ecosystem functions we find here strongly call for better integrating FD measurements into field studies and across scales to understand the effects of changing zooplankton biodiversity on marine ecosystem functioning.

4.16 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #16

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Carbon biomass of two eukaryotic calcifying taxa (pteropoda and foraminifera) in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m), available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides two NetCDF files that record the ensemble predictions of global monthly (12 time levels) biomass concentrations of calcifying Pteropoda (in mg C m^{-3}) and Foraminifera (in $\mu\text{g C m}^{-3}$). The monthly biomass concentration fields were obtained by training a suite of five distribution models tailored for predicting plankton biomass data obtained from traditional sampling techniques (see Knecht et al., 2023 for details). The observational data and the environmental layers used to train the biomass models were integrated over the epipelagic layer (0-200m) of the global ocean. Therefore, the predicted values are representative of the conditions prevailing in the epipelagic layer. The two NetCDF files thus record the: minimum (Min), maximum (Max), mean, median and the standard deviation (Stdev) of the monthly predictions issued from these five models.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Global mean annual total carbon (TC) biomass concentration for pteropods (left, A) and foraminifers (right, B), averaged over all months and models. Values are shown as $\log_{10}(\text{TC} + 1)$, note also the different color scales for pteropods and foraminifers. Stippled regions in plots A - D indicate grid points where the environmental conditions were outside the training

dataset for more than six months of the year as calculated with the Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surfaces (MESS) analysis. The lower panel plots C and D show the mean annual relative standard deviation of the model predictions for pteropods (left) and foraminifers (right), normalized with the mean prediction value at each grid point to facilitate comparison. Figure from Knecht et al. (2023).

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, carbon biomass, ocean microbiome, pteropoda, foraminifera
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 2
- **File size:** 18 MB/file = total 36 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 120 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 2 [pteropoda and foraminifera]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [carbon biomass*]
- **Statistic(s):** 5 [minimum, maximum, median, mean, standard deviation]
- **Time period(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200m)]

* units for are mg C m⁻³ for pteropoda and µg C m⁻³ for foraminifera

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2017)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 5 models
 - General Linear Models (GLM)
 - General Additive Models (GAM)
 - Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
 - Random Forest (RF)
 - Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 4 predictors (see list below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Temperature (°C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA18](#))
- Chlorophyll-a (SeaWiFs; NASA OB.DAAC 2018)
- Mixed Layer Depth (MLD; from SODA3.4.2 (Carton et al. 2018)) for pteropoda only
- Eddy kinetic energy (EKE; from Copernicus (Copernicus 2021)) for foraminifera only

Additional predictors tested for inclusion were salinity, dissolved oxygen at 200 m depth, nitrate, and phosphate from WOA, the depth of the euphotic zone (z_{eu}), photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), particulate backscattering coefficient at 443 nm (BBP_{443}) and the diffuse attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiation at 490 nm (Kd_{490}) from SeaWiFS, total alkalinity, dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), the partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂) and the calcite and aragonite saturation state ($\Omega_{calcite}$ and $\Omega_{aragonite}$) from Ocean-SODA-ETHZ (Gregor and Gruber 2021).

Depth-resolved monthly climatological predictors from the WOA18 were averaged over the climatological mixed layer depth (MLD).

The distribution of chlorophyll-a concentrations, nutrient variables, MLD, and eddy kinetic energy (EKE) were log-transformed.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Knecht, N.S., Benedetti, F., Hofmann Elizondo, U., Bednaršek, N., Chaabane, S., de Weerd, C., Peijnenburg, K.T., Schiebel, R. and Vogt, M., 2023. The impact of zooplankton calcifiers on the marine carbon cycle. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 37(6), <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GB007685>.

Abstract: Shelled pteropods and planktic foraminifers are calcifying zooplankton that contribute to the biological carbon pump via the sinking of their calcareous shells. However, their importance for regional and global plankton biomass and carbon fluxes is not well understood. Here, we modeled global annual patterns of pteropod and foraminifer total carbon (TC) biomass and total inorganic carbon (TIC) export fluxes over the top 200 m using five species distribution models (SDMs). An extended version of the MARine Ecosystem DATA (MAREDAT; Buitenhuis et al. 2013) of zooplankton abundance observations was used to estimate the biomass of both plankton groups. We found hotspots of mean annual pteropod biomass in the high Northern latitudes and the global upwelling systems, and in the high latitudes of both hemispheres and the tropics for foraminifers. This largely agrees with previously observed distributions. For both groups, temperature is the strongest environmental correlate, followed by chlorophyll-a. We found mean annual standing stocks of 52 Tg TC (48 to 57 Tg TC) and 0.9 Tg TC (0.6 to 1.1 Tg TC) for pteropods and foraminifers, respectively. This translates to mean annual TIC fluxes of 14 Tg TIC yr⁻¹ (9 to 22 Tg TIC yr⁻¹) for pteropod shells and 11 Tg TIC yr⁻¹ (3 to 27 Tg TIC yr⁻¹) for foraminifer tests. These results are similar to previous estimates for foraminifers, but approximately a factor of ten lower for pteropods. Pteropods contribute 0.2%–3.2% and foraminifers 0.1%–3.8% to global surface carbonate fluxes. Including global coccolithophore fluxes, this leaves 40%–60% of the global carbonate fluxes unaccounted for. Our figures are likely lower-bound estimates due to sampling data characteristics and uncertainty associated with organism growth rates.

4.17 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #17

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Carbon biomass of 20 taxonomic groups of zooplankton in the epipelagic layer (0-200 m) and mesopelagic layer (200-500), available as annual averages projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental conditions, using an ensemble of habitat suitability models.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides 20 NetCDF files that record the predicted global mean annual biomass concentrations (in $\text{mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) of diverse zooplankton groups across variable ocean depth layers that were compiled by the FP7/H2020 TRIATLAS project: Acantharea (0-500m), Annelida (0-200m), Appendicularia (0-500m), Chaetognatha (0-500m), Cnidaria (other than Hydrozoa and Siphonophorae; 0-200m), Collodaria (solitary forms; 0-500m), Collodaria (colonial forms; 0-200m), Copepoda (0-500m), Crustacea (other than Copepoda and Malacostraca; 0-500m), Ctenophora (0-200m), Doliolida (0-200m), Eumalacostraca (0-500m), Foraminifera (0-500m), Hydrozoa (other than Siphonophorae; 0-500m), Limacinidae (0-200m), Mollusca (other than Limacinidae; 0-200m), Ostracoda (0-500m), Phaeodaria (0-500m), Rhizaria (other than Foraminifera and Collodaria; 0-500m), and Siphonophorae (0-500m). These predictions of mean annual biomass concentrations were obtained by training Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) on observations of zooplankton organisms taken by multiple Underwater Vision Profiler version 5 (UVP5) throughout the globe and matched against annual climatological values of the environmental conditions. Because of the design of the underlying scientific study (Drago et al., 2022), the UVP5 data were partitioned between the epipelagic (0-200 m) and mesopelagic (200-500 m) layers of the ocean. As a result, the BRT were trained on zooplankton biomass concentrations estimated for these two layers separately. BRT predictions were thus also made and evaluated for these two layers separately. When mean annual carbon concentrations were skillfully predicted for both layers, they were recorded as such in the present NetCDF (i.e., values over 0-500m instead of 0-200m). Please see Drago et al. (2022) for further technical details.

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Distribution map of the predicted minimum global biomass between 0 and 500m using taxa which obtained a significant result (p -value < 0.05) in Pearson test between the predicted biomass and the biomass calculated from UUP5 data. Figure from Drago et al. (2022)

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, biogeography, global distribution, habitat suitability model, carbon biomass, eukaryotes, plankton, contemporary climate conditions, TRIATLAS
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** Please note that this collection of maps has not been created in the context of, nor funded by AtlantECO.
- **Acknowledgements:** This publication has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817578 (project TRIATLAS). This output reflects only the author’s view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 20
- **File size:** 400-900 KB/file = total 13.3 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 60 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 20 [taxonomic groups]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [carbon biomass (mgC/m³)]
- **Statistic(s):** 3 [mean, standard error, standard deviation]
- **Time period(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [annual average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m) or pelagic layer (0-500 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2017)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** 1 model
 - Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 9 predictors
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

Zooplankton biomass was estimated by in situ imaging and machine learning as described in Drago, L., et al. 2022. Global distribution of zooplankton biomass estimated by in situ imaging and machine learning. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.894372>

https://github.com/dlaetitia/Global_zooplankton_biomass_distribution

List of taxa whose biomass is integrated over the epipelagic layer (0-200 m)

- Annelida
- Cnidaria other than Hydrozoa and Siphonophorae
- Collodaria colonial forms
- Ctenophora
- Doliolida
- Limacinidae
- Mollusca other than Limacinidae

List of taxa whose biomass is integrated over the pelagic layer (0-500 m)

- Acantharea
- Appendicularia
- Chaetognatha
- Collodaria solitary forms
- Copepoda
- Crustacea other than Copepoda and Malacostraca
- Eumalacostraca
- Foraminifera
- Hydrozoa other than Siphonophorae
- Ostracoda
- Phaeodaria
- Rhizaria other than Foraminifera and Collodaria
- Siphonophorae

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Temperature (°C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA2018](#))
- Salinity (psu) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA2018](#))
- Oxygen (converted from $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ to kPa for better physiological interpretation) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA2018](#))
- Nitrate ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA2018](#))
- Phosphate ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA2018](#))
- Silicate ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA2018](#))
- Surface chlorophyll-a data (Chl *a* in mg m^{-3}) from the Copernicus database (OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_CHL_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_082)
- Bathymetry data from NOAA (Amante and Eakins, 2009) with a spatial resolution of 10 minutes; both were re-gridded to a 1° grid.
- Distance to coast calculated using the raster package (Hijmans, 2021)

Predictors were configured with a 1°x1° horizontal grid, a 0-500 m depth range, and a monthly temporal resolution. The temporal coverage of salinity and temperature predictors was 2005 to 2017, and 1955 to 2017 for the other predictors. Monthly averaged surface chlorophyll-a data (Chl *a* in mg m^{-3}) resolved to 1/24° from 2005 to 2017. To obtain annual climatologies, when relevant, each monthly variable was averaged over its time period of coverage.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Drago, L., Panaïotis, T., Irisson, J.O., Babin, M., Biard, T., Carlotti, F., Coppola, L., Guidi, L., Hauss, H., Karp-Boss, L. and Lombard, F., 2022. Global distribution of zooplankton biomass estimated by in situ imaging and machine learning. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.894372>.

Abstract: Zooplankton plays a major role in ocean food webs and biogeochemical cycles, and provides major ecosystem services as a main driver of the biological carbon pump and in sustaining fish communities. Zooplankton is also sensitive to its environment and reacts to its changes. To better understand the importance of zooplankton, and to inform prognostic models that try to represent them, spatially-resolved biomass estimates of key plankton taxa are desirable. In this study we predict, for the first time, the global biomass distribution of 19 zooplankton taxa (1-50 mm Equivalent Spherical Diameter) using observations with the Underwater Vision Profiler 5, a quantitative *in situ* imaging instrument. After classification of 466,872 organisms from more than 3,549 profiles (0-500 m) obtained between 2008 and 2019 throughout the globe, we estimated their individual biovolumes and converted them to biomass using taxa-specific conversion factors. We then associated these biomass estimates with climatologies of environmental variables (temperature, salinity, oxygen, etc.), to build habitat models using boosted regression trees. The results reveal maximal zooplankton biomass values around 60°N and 55°S as well as minimal values around the oceanic gyres. An increased zooplankton biomass is also predicted for the equator. Global integrated biomass (0-500 m) was estimated at 0.403 PgC. It was largely dominated by Copepoda (35.7%, mostly in polar regions), followed by Eumalacostraca (26.6%) Rhizaria (16.4%, mostly in the intertropical convergence zone). The machine learning approach used here is sensitive to the size of the training set and generates reliable predictions for abundant groups such as Copepoda ($R^2 \approx 20-66\%$) but not for rare ones (Ctenophora, Cnidaria, $R^2 < 5\%$). Still, this study offers a first protocol to estimate global, spatially resolved zooplankton biomass and community composition from *in situ* imaging observations of individual organisms. The underlying dataset covers a period of 10 years while approaches that rely on net samples utilized datasets gathered since the 1960s. Increased use of digital imaging approaches should enable us to obtain zooplankton biomass distribution estimates at basin to global scales in shorter time frames in the future.

4.18 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #18

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Climato-Genomic Provinces projected under contemporary (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) environmental conditions.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides the projected probabilities of presence of the 27 “climato-genomic provinces” described in Fremont et al. (2022) and originally defined in Richter et al (2022). They are projected using 10 year average ensemble climatologies (CMIP5) in the present day (2006-15) and in the future (2090-99, RCP8.5). Provinces encompass 6 size fractions of plankton that were sampled during the Tara Oceans expeditions (2009-2013): 0-0.2 μm enriched in viruses, 0.22-3 μm enriched in bacteria, 0.8-5 μm enriched in protists, 5-20 μm , 20-180 μm and 180-2000 μm enriched in small metazoans (mainly copepods).

This collection, and other collections of *Global maps of the Ocean microbiome* are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Global biogeographies of size-structured plankton provinces projected on WOA13 dataset. Figure 2 in Frémont et al. (2022).

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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, global distribution, climato genomic provinces, ocean microbiome, virus, bacteria, protists, metazoans, contemporary climate conditions, future climate projections
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 54
- **File size:** 2 MB/file = total 108 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 54 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 27 [climato genomic provinces]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [presence (0 or 1)]
- **Statistic(s):** 1 [projected value]
- **Time periods(s):** 2 [contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099)]

- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [10 year average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0-200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** comparison of contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099; RCP8.5)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 4 models
 - Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)
 - Random Forest (RF)
 - Neural Networks (NN)
 - General Additive Models (GAM)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 7 predictors
- **Climate model(s):** ensemble of 6 Earth System Models
 - CESM1-BGC (Gent et al., 2011)
 - GFDL-ESM2G & GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013)
 - HadGEM2-ES (Collins et al., 2011)
 - IPSL-CM5A-LR & IPSL-CM5A-MR (Dufresne et al., 2013)
 - MPI-ESM-LR & MPI-ESM-MR (Giorgetta et al., 2013)
 - NorESM1-ME (Bentsen et al., 2013)

Associated References - Microbiome observations

27 genomic provinces from Fremont et al. (2022)

- A3-size-fraction-0-0.2-enriched-in-virus
- A4-size-fraction-0-0.2-enriched-in-virus
- A6-size-fraction-0-0.2-enriched-in-virus
- A7-size-fraction-0-0.2-enriched-in-virus
- A8-size-fraction-0-0.2-enriched-in-virus
- C1-size-fraction-0.8-5-enriched-in-protists
- C3-size-fraction-0.8-5-enriched-in-protists
- C4-size-fraction-0.8-5-enriched-in-protists
- C8-size-fraction-0.8-5-enriched-in-protists
- C9-size-fraction-0.8-5-enriched-in-protists
- C10-size-fraction-0.8-5-enriched-in-protists
- C11-size-fraction-0.8-5-enriched-in-protists
- B2-size-fraction-0.22-3-enriched-in-bacteria
- B3-size-fraction-0.22-3-enriched-in-bacteria
- B5-size-fraction-0.22-3-enriched-in-bacteria
- B6-size-fraction-0.22-3-enriched-in-bacteria
- B7-size-fraction-0.22-3-enriched-in-bacteria
- B8-size-fraction-0.22-3-enriched-in-bacteria
- D3-size-fraction-5-20-enriched-in-small-metazoans
- D4-size-fraction-5-20-enriched-in-small-metazoans
- D6-size-fraction-5-20-enriched-in-small-metazoans
- E1-size-fraction-20-180-enriched-in-small-metazoans
- E5-size-fraction-20-180-enriched-in-small-metazoans
- E6-size-fraction-20-180-enriched-in-small-metazoans
- F1-size-fraction-180-2000-enriched-in-small-metazoans
- F5-size-fraction-180-2000-enriched-in-small-metazoans

- F8-size-fraction-180-2000-enriched-in-small-metazoans

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Dissolved iron (Fe) from the biogeochemical model PISCES-v2 (Aumont et al. 2015)
- Seasonality index of nitrate (SI NO_3), defined as the range of nitrate concentrations over the year in one grid cell divided by the maximum range encountered in WOA13.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Frémont, P., Gehlen, M., Vrac, M., Leconte, J., Delmont, T.O., Wincker, P., Iudicone, D. and Jaillon, O., 2022. Restructuring of plankton genomic biogeography in the surface ocean under climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 12(4), pp.393-401, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8>.

Abstract: The impact of climate change on diversity, functioning and biogeography of marine plankton remains a major unresolved issue. Here environmental niches are evidenced for plankton communities at the genomic scale for six size fractions from viruses to meso-zooplankton. The spatial extrapolation of these niches portrays ocean partitionings south of 60° N into *climato-genomic* provinces characterized by signature genomes. By 2090, under the RCP8.5 future climate scenario, provinces are reorganized over half of the ocean area considered, and almost all provinces are displaced poleward. Particularly, tropical provinces expand at the expense of temperate ones. Sea surface temperature is identified as the main driver of changes (50%), followed by phosphate (11%) and salinity (10%). Compositional shifts among key planktonic groups suggest impacts on the nitrogen and carbon cycles. Provinces are linked to estimates of carbon export fluxes which are projected to decrease, on average, by 4% in response to biogeographical restructuring.

4.19 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #19

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index comparing climato-genomic provinces projected under contemporary (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) environmental conditions.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides a global Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index (accounting for projected changes in the different size fraction) comparing present day and end of century projected provinces is included. This index is also projected on EEZ and main fisheries (from Watson, 2017).

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index comparing present day (2006-15) and end of the century (2090-99) projections of climato-genomic provinces under RCP8.5 greenhouse gas emission scenario.

Authors

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4. Jade Leconte (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3132-0114>) Génomique Métabolique, Genoscope, Institut François-Jacob, CEA, CNRS, Université d'Evry, Université Paris-Saclay, 91057 Evry, France.
5. Tom O. Delmont (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7053-7848>) Génomique Métabolique, Genoscope, Institut François-Jacob, CEA, CNRS, Université d'Evry, Université Paris-Saclay, 91057 Evry, France.
6. Patrick Wincker (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7562-3454>) Génomique Métabolique, Genoscope, Institut François-Jacob, CEA, CNRS, Université d'Evry, Université Paris-Saclay, 91057 Evry, France.
7. Daniele Iudicone (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7473-394X>) Stazione Zoologica Anton Dhorn, Naples, Italy.
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Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, global distribution, climato genomic provinces, time periods dissimilarity, ocean microbiome, virus, bacteria, protists, metazoans, contemporary climate conditions, future climate projections
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** not provided
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File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 3
- **File size:** 2 MB/file = total 6 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 3 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 1 [climato genomic provinces dissimilarity]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index]
- **Statistic(s):** 1 [projected value]
- **Time periods(s):** 1 [comparison of contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 1 [comparison of two 10 year average]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 3 [360x180 (1x1 degree), Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs), fisheries areas]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [epipelagic layer (0 - 200 m)]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** comparison of contemporary (2006-2015) & end of century (2090-2099)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 4 models
 - Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)
 - Random Forest (RF)
 - Neural Networks (NN)
 - General Additive Models (GAM)
- **Environmental predictor(s):** ensemble of 7 predictors
- **Climate model(s):** ensemble of 6 Earth System Models
 - CESM1-BGC (Gent et al., 2011)
 - GFDL-ESM2G & GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013)
 - HadGEM2-ES (Collins et al., 2011)
 - IPSL-CM5A-LR & IPSL-CM5A-MR (Dufresne et al., 2013)
 - MPI-ESM-LR & MPI-ESM-MR (Giorgetta et al., 2013)
 - NorESM1-ME (Bentsen et al., 2013)

Associated References - Microbiome observations

27 genomic provinces from Fremont et al. (2022)

Associated References - Environmental predictors

- Sea surface temperature (SST, °C) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Sea surface salinity (SSS) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of nitrate (NO_3^- , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of phosphate (PO_4^{3-} , μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Surface concentrations of silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, μM) from the World Ocean Atlas ([WOA13v2](#))
- Dissolved iron (Fe) from the biogeochemical model PISCES-v2 (Aumont et al. 2015)
- Seasonality index of nitrate (SI NO_3^-), defined as the range of nitrate concentrations over the year in one grid cell divided by the maximum range encountered in WOA13.

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Frémont, P., Gehlen, M., Vrac, M., Leconte, J., Delmont, T.O., Wincker, P., Iudicone, D. and Jaillon, O., 2022. Restructuring of plankton genomic biogeography in the surface ocean under climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 12(4), pp.393-401, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8>.

Abstract: The impact of climate change on diversity, functioning and biogeography of marine plankton remains a major unresolved issue. Here environmental niches are evidenced for plankton communities at the genomic scale for six size fractions from viruses to meso-zooplankton. The spatial extrapolation of these niches portrays ocean partitionings south of 60° N into *climato-genomic* provinces characterized by signature genomes. By 2090, under the RCP8.5 future climate scenario, provinces are reorganized over half of the ocean area considered, and almost all provinces are displaced poleward. Particularly, tropical provinces expand at the expense of temperate ones. Sea surface temperature is identified as the main driver of changes (50%), followed by phosphate (11%) and salinity (10%). Compositional shifts among key planktonic groups suggest impacts on the nitrogen and carbon cycles. Provinces are linked to estimates of carbon export fluxes which are projected to decrease, on average, by 4% in response to biogeographical restructuring.

4.20 Global maps of the Ocean microbiome (AtlantECO-MAPS) Collection #20

Collection title

Global maps of the Ocean microbiome: Concentration of microplastic in surface waters, available as monthly climatologies projected under contemporary (2005-2017) environmental and anthropogenic predictors.

Abstract

This collection of global maps provides global predictions of surface monthly microplastics concentrations (in #items.km⁻², log₁₀ transformed) modelled through five distribution models (GLM, GAM, ANN, RF, GBM). The models were trained on an observational dataset that aggregated measurements from multiple microplastic sampling campaigns compiled by van Sebille et al. (2015) and completed by Schmiz (2021). The original dataset of Schmiz (2021) synthesised no less than 13 159 microplastic concentrations observations spanning from 1979 to 2019. These microplastic concentrations measurements were collected through diverse sampling methods (~83% come from plankton nets) and covered plastics particles ranging from 32µm to 20cm. Giacomo Poli (MSc student, ETH Zürich) analysed this dataset and adapted the modelling pipeline of Knecht et al., (2023) to model global surface microplastics concentrations based on five types of statistical models and an exhaustive suite of environmental and anthropogenic predictors.

This collection, and other collections of **Global maps of the Ocean microbiome** are described in the AtlantECO-MAPS publication (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18696236>).

Graphical abstract

Caption: Global annual ensemble mean microplastic concentrations across all models and predictor sets. Values are shown as log₁₀ and expressed as items/km². Black points indicate the regions where the standard deviation between sets and models >0.75, indicating a higher set and/or model disagreement and therefore lower prediction confidence. From G. Poli, MSc thesis, 2023.

Authors

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7. Nicolas Gruber (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2085-2310>) Environmental Physics, Institute of Biogeochemistry and Pollutant Dynamics, ETH Zurich, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland.

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- **Affiliation:** Environmental Physics, Institute of Biogeochemistry and Pollutant Dynamics, ETH Zurich, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland

Additional information

- **Disciplines:** Biological Oceanography
- **Devices:** Biological and biogeochemical models (MOD08) & Global models (MOD01)
- **Parameters:** Biodiversity indices (BDRV)
- **Keywords:** AtlantECO-MAPS, global distribution, microplastics, contemporary climate conditions
- **License:** Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
- **Utilisation note:** not provided
- **Acknowledgements:** This publication has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862923 (project AtlantECO). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

File(s) specifications

- **Number of file(s):** 1
- **File size:** 60 MB
- **File format:** NetCDF (*.nc)

Map(s) specifications

- **Number of map(s):** 12 [global maps]
- **Mapped Entity(ies):** 1 [microplastics]
- **Mapped Variable(s):** 1 [concentration (#/km², log₁₀ transformed)]
- **Statistic(s):** 1 [minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation]
- **Time periods(s):** 1 [contemporary (2005-2017)]
- **Temporal grid(s):** 12 [monthly]
- **Horizontal grid(s):** 1 [360x180 (1x1 degree)]
- **Vertical grid(s):** 1 [surface waters]

Model(s) specifications

- **Time period(s):** contemporary (2005-2017)
- **Habitat Suitability Model(s):** ensemble of 5 models
 - General Linear Model (GLM)
 - General Additive Model (GAM)
 - Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
 - Random Forest (RF)
 - Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)
- **Environmental & anthropogenic predictor(s):** ensemble of 30 predictors (see list below)
- **Climate model(s):** not applicable

Associated References - Microbiome observations

not provided

Associated References - Environmental & anthropogenic predictors

Table 1. Pool of all predictors divided into the 7 categories. The variable nickname is the name used to refer to the predictor.

Category	Candidate predictor	Variable nickname	Reference
Atmospheric	Eastward wind speed	wind_u10_era5	Hersbach et al. (2020)
	Northward wind speed	wind_v10_era5	Hersbach et al. (2020)
	Wind speed	windspeed_era5	Hersbach et al. (2020)
	Wind direction	wind_direction	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Bathymetry	Sea floor depth	bathymetry_min_etopo1	Amante and Eakins (2009)
Biological activity	Chlorophyll	chlorophyll_seawifs	NASA OB.DAAC (2018a)
Human activity	Distance to closest coast	dist2coast	Amante and Eakins (2009)
	Distance to closest largest city	dist2cities	Amante and Eakins (2009), opendatasoft
	Distance to closest largest river	dist2rivers	Amante and Eakins (2009); Fekete et al. (2002)
	Fishing hours	fishing_hours	Kroodsmma et al. (2018)
Location	Latitude	degree_north	-
	Longitude	degree_east	-
Physical and biogeochemical	Dissolved inorganic carbon	dic_surf_osethz	Gregor and Gruber (2021)
	Dissolved oxygen concentrations	oxygen	Garcia et al. (2019b)
	Mixed layer depth	mld_soda	Carton et al. (2018)
	Nitrate concentrations	nitrate	Garcia et al. (2019b)
	Phosphate concentrations	phosphate	Garcia et al. (2019b)
	Sea surface salinity	sss_cci_smos	Olmedo et al. (2017)
	Sea surface temperature	sst_oisstv2	Huang et al. (2020)
	Mixed layer photosynthetic active radiation	mlpar1	NASA OB.DAAC (2018b)
Transport	Photosynthetic active radiation	PAR	NASA OB.DAAC (2018b)
	Currents direction	currents_direction	AVISO (2016)
	Currents divergence	divergence	AVISO (2016)
	Currents relative vorticity	relative_vorticity	AVISO (2016)
	Eastward geostrophic currents velocity	ugos	AVISO (2016)
	Eddy kinetic energy	EKE	EKE AVISO (2016); Qiu and Chen (2004)
	Geostrophic currents velocity	total_currents	AVISO (2016)
	Northward geostrophic currents velocity	vgos	AVISO (2016)
	Sea level anomaly	sla	AVISO (2016)
	Wind divergence	wind_divergence	Hersbach et al. (2020)

Associated References - Software/Code

not provided

Associated References - Scientific Publication

Poli et al. (in prep); G. Poli, MSc thesis, 2023; [doi:10.5281/zenodo.10245292](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245292).

Abstract: Marine microplastics pose a serious risk to the health of marine ecosystems, yet little is known about the concentration and spatial distribution of global surface ocean microplastics concentrations. Here, we use a data-driven, statistical approach to estimate global surface ocean microplastic concentrations and microplastic count per ocean basin by training an ensemble of statistical and machine learning models based on comprehensive observational datasets and a range of global environmental predictor variables. We found a clear pattern of microplastics accumulation in the subtropical gyres and in the Mediterranean Sea and lower microplastics concentrations in tropical and polar ocean regions. Oxygen and sea surface temperature were the strongest covariates of microplastics (34% and 33.2% of variance explained), indicative of strong latitudinal patterns and water age characteristics, followed by other physical and biogeochemical predictors (nitrate concentrations, dissolved inorganic carbon concentrations and mixed layer photosynthetically active radiation). We quantified a global mean surface microplastics concentration of $21\,250 \pm 1\,387$ items.km⁻², resulting in a global average microplastics inventory of 11.38 ± 0.76 trillion particles floating in the surface ocean. Our new inventory largely agrees with previously observed and modelled distributions using Lagrangian models but might represent a lower-bound estimate, given the lack of predictors associated with human plastic inputs in our approach. Our statistical approach has proven to be promising and might represent a computationally cheap complementary approach to the most used Lagrangian models, once predictors directly associated with human plastic inputs into the ocean are better constrained.

4.21 Global maps of environmental predictors

Global distribution of environmental parameters

5 Data visualisation tools (web applications)

In order to process, interpret and visualize data, a range of web applications have been developed by the WP2 team (task 2.3; D2.2; lead: ETHZ/SU/UNIROMA1). These tools include:

- A PlotlyApp to serve biodiversity data from species distribution modelling to policymakers: <https://mapmaker-new.ethz.ch/>
- A user-friendly ShinyApp designed to support novice species distribution modellers. This application offers a guided step-by-step pipeline for calibrating and evaluating species distribution models. It is tailored for use with presence-only and presence-absence data and publicly available high-resolution predictor variables from Bio-ORACLE (<https://www.bio-oracle.org/>). Additionally, it allows users to upload custom predictors directly through the application interface (De Angelis et al., in preparation): <https://dandangelis.shinyapps.io/emocean/>. To overcome current memory limitations on shinyapps.io servers, the tool can be run locally using R software (<https://www.r-project.org/>), by running the following code lines:
 - `install.packages("shiny")`
 - `shiny::runGist("b4f2fddf2de6b20c49917a128bf41d62")`
- A ShinyApp for the visualisation of present day and end of century (RCP8.5 climate change scenario) niche areas of eukaryote plankton MAGs from Fremont et al. (2022) and Delmont et al. (2022): <https://gigaplankton.shinyapps.io/TOENDB/>

6 Data analysis software

A standardized, automated, and flexible framework for multi-species habitat modelling, the CEPHALOPOD model pipeline (Schickele et al. 2025), developed in synergy by AtlantECO ((task 2.3; D2.2; lead: ETHZ/SU) and the EU project BlueCloud2026 (<https://blue-cloud.org/>), unifies existing methods for presence only (Benedetti et al., 2021), continuous (Knecht et al., 2023) and proportion data (Schickele et al., 2025) within a common habitat modelling framework tailored for the marine environment. CEPHALOPOD is built on automated access to observational data from federating initiatives such as AtlantECO, OBIS, and GBIF. It is associated with state-of-the-art statistical and machine learning methods to extract and model information from heterogeneous, scarce and biased field observations, including presence only (occurrences), quantitative (abundance and biomass) and relative (e.g., percentage of gene reads) data. It is highly automated and follows explicit quality checks informing the user of the predictive accuracy and interpretability of the results. The framework is described and benchmarked in the reference publication (Schickele et al. 2025), can be downloaded and used on local machines, and is ported in a cloud computing infrastructure (<https://blue-cloud.org/> - ecosystem workbench). It is currently used by ETHZ and SU partners to map Nitrogen metabolism from genomic data (Schickele et al. in prep), global plankton diversity and biomass (Schickele et al. in prep, Eriksson et al. in prep, Clerc et al. in prep), and global plankton transparency (Sonnet et al. in prep), among other applications. CEPHALOPOD provides an unprecedented opportunity to foster collaborations in the field of marine science, with training session already performed to PhD and Master students within ETH Zurich, during the AtlantECO Synergy Summer School (Ischia, 2025; <https://www.atlanteco.eu/synergy-summer-school-2025>) and with an Ocean Teacher Global Academy (OTGA) course in preparation (<https://classroom.oceanteacher.org/>).

A predictor library, available for use with CEPHALOPOD, for species distribution modelling of marine target variables that extends the currently available high-resolution Bio-ORACLE compilation (<https://www.bio-oracle.org/>; Assis et al., 2017) with climate grid resolution predictor variables (monthly, regular horizontal and WOA depth grid) has been constructed in our EU sister projects BlueCloud2026 and BioOcean5D and is available at <https://data.up.ethz.ch/doku.php?id=biocean:readme>.

7 AtlantECO-CMIP6-SDM

An ensemble of environmental climatologies has been extracted from model outputs from CMIP6 and regridded for the extrapolation of biological data to different future climates (task 2.3; D2.2; lead: ETHZ/SU/UBern). The resulting dataset, CMIP6-SDM, is standardized in a common format for use by the marine species distribution models (SDM) community. For each variable in each model, one-degree resolution monthly climatologies are available for three periods (1991-2010, 2041-2060 and 2081-2100), three scenarios (Historical + SSP1.26 and Historical + SSP5.85) and three depths layers (0-10m, 0-100m and 200-300m).

Please note that this dataset is not intended for any other use; users seeking broader CMIP6 data should access the ESGF repository directly. The dataset is available upon request at <https://data.up.ethz.ch/doku.php?id=bioceancmip:readme>

Pre-treatment:

Models :

- 1) IPSL-CM6A-LR (French)
- 2) CNRM-ESM2-1 (French)
- 3) MIROC-ES2L (Japanese)
- 4) ACCESS-ESM1-5 (Australian)
- 5) GFDL-ESM4 (American)
- 6) MPI-ESM1-2-LR (German)
- 7) MPI-ESM1-2-HR (German)
- 8) CESM2 (American)
- 9) CanESM5 (Canadian)
- 10) NorESM2-LM (Norwegian)

Variables:

- Chlorophyll Concentration (chl)
- Detritus Carbon Concentration (detoc)
- Dissolved Iron Concentration (dfe)
- Dissolved Inorganic Carbon Concentration (dissic)
- Dissolved Organic Carbon Concentration (dissoc)
- Mixed Layer Thickness (mlotst)
- Nitrate Concentration (no3)
- Dissolved Oxygen Concentration (o2)
- pH
- Phytoplankton Carbon Concentration (phyc)
- Phosphate Concentration (po4)
- Primary Production (pp)
- Downward Shortwave Radiation at the Ocean Surface (rsdo)
- Silicate Concentration (si)
- Sea Water Salinity (so)
- Sea Surface Partial Pressure of CO2 (spco2)
- Total Alkalinity (talk)
- Sea Water Potential Temperature (thetao)
- Zooplankton Carbon Concentration (zooc)
- Sea Surface Height (zos)

Dimension:

“lat”: 180x1°, -90° to 90°

“lon”:360x1°, -180° to 180°

“time”: monthly resolution

“depth” : one layer per file

The open access initial compilation of regridded future projections for selected CMIP6 models, variables and future scenarios can be found under: <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/AtlantECO-CMIP6/>.

Models: GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR,

Scenarios: historical, piControl, SSP126, SSP245

Time period: 1850-2014 (historical), 2015 - 2100 (future projections)

Variables: intpn2, intpp, mlotst, no3, o2, ph, phyc, so, spco2, thetao, tos, zooc, zos

Grid: regular degree grid; 360 (lon)x180 (lat) x 12 (months), with variable-specific depth resolution (surface versus full water column)

For further information about variables, grids, simulation set-ups, please consult the CMIP6 website (<https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phase-6-cmip6/>) as well as Eyring et al. (2016) for simulation design and naming conventions.

8 Conclusion

This second and final version of AtlantECO-MAPS (D2.5) provides a comprehensive collection of extrapolated maps about past, present and future distributions of microplastics (present day only) & biological parameters including presence/absence, abundance, biomass, richness and diversity of marine microbiome taxa and functions. All collections of maps are archived, citable and accessible at SEANOE - Sea Scientific Open Data Publication (<https://www.seanoe.org/>). A selection of maps of interest for ocean literacy and policy making are hosted on the AtlantECO GeoNode (<https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>) in support of FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. This collection inspired and enabled the development of multiple data visualisation applications and triggered the development of automatised mapping pipelines such as the one developed within the sister project BlueCloud2026 (Schickele et al. 2025), which is currently used and applied by AtlantECO partners, as well as by members of EU HORIZON sister projects BlueCloud2026 and BiOcean5D. All data and software products are publicly available and many additional scientific projects exploring and discovering patterns in further data sets part of AtlantECO-BASE have been started, both within and beyond the project. While some of these results will arrive too late for the inclusion in this deliverable, AtlantECO-MAPS formed the knowledge base for the scientific exploitation of AtlantECO data in a multitude of macroecological applications, with the results to inspire the science community and all predictors, pipelines, model outputs and data visualisation applications to be used by the scientific and stakeholder community for years to come.

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Appendix 1

List of taxonomic entities AtlantECO-MAPS Collection #1

- *Acanthoica_quattropina*
- *Achnanthes_longipes*
- *Actiniscus_pentasterias*
- *Actinoptychus_octonarius*
- *Actinoptychus_senarius*
- *Actinoptychus_splendens*
- *Akashiwo_sanguinea*
- *Amphisolenia_bidentata*
- *Amphisolenia_bispinosa*
- *Archaeoperidinium_minutum*
- *Asterionellopsis_glacialis*
- *Asterolampra_marylandica*
- *Asteromphalus_brookei*
- *Asteromphalus_flabellatus*
- *Asteromphalus_heptactis*
- *Bacillaria_paxillifera*
- *Bacteriastrum_comosum*
- *Bacteriastrum_delicatulum*
- *Bacteriastrum_elegans*
- *Bacteriastrum_elongatum*
- *Bacteriastrum_furcatum*
- *Bacteriastrum_hyalinum*
- *Bacteriastrum_mediterraneum*
- *Biddulphia_alternans*
- *Calcidiscus_leptoporus*
- *Calciosolenia_brasiliensis*
- *Calciosolenia_murrayi*
- *Cerataulina_pelagica*
- *Ceratium_arcticum*
- *Ceratium_breve*
- *Ceratium_contrarium*
- *Ceratium_falcatiforme*
- *Ceratium_falcatum*
- *Ceratium_gibberum*
- *Ceratium_horridum*
- *Ceratium_longirostrum*
- *Ceratium_massiliense*
- *Ceratium_setaceum*
- *Ceratium_symmetricum*
- *Ceratium_trichoceros*
- *Ceratocorys_armata*
- *Ceratocorys_horrida*
- *Ceratocorys_reticulata*
- *Chaetoceros_aequatorialis*
- *Chaetoceros_affinis*

- Chaetoceros_anastomosans
- Chaetoceros_atlanticus
- Chaetoceros_borealis
- Chaetoceros_brevis
- Chaetoceros_coarctatus
- Chaetoceros_compressus
- Chaetoceros_concavicornis
- Chaetoceros_constrictus
- Chaetoceros_convolutus
- Chaetoceros_costatus
- Chaetoceros_curvisetus
- Chaetoceros_dadayi
- Chaetoceros_danicus
- Chaetoceros_debilis
- Chaetoceros_decipiens
- Chaetoceros_densus
- Chaetoceros_diadema
- Chaetoceros_dichaeta
- Chaetoceros_didymus
- Chaetoceros_diversus
- Chaetoceros_eibenii
- Chaetoceros_laciniosus
- Chaetoceros_laevis
- Chaetoceros_lauderi
- Chaetoceros_lorenzianus
- Chaetoceros_messanensis
- Chaetoceros_pelagicus
- Chaetoceros_pendulus
- Chaetoceros_peruvianus
- Chaetoceros_pseudocurvisetus
- Chaetoceros_pseudodichaetus
- Chaetoceros_radicans
- Chaetoceros_rostratus
- Chaetoceros_saltans
- Chaetoceros_seychellarum
- Chaetoceros_simplex
- Chaetoceros_socialis
- Chaetoceros_subsecundus
- Chaetoceros_teres
- Chaetoceros_tetrastichon
- Chaetoceros_tortissimus
- Chaetoceros_vanheurckii
- Chaetoceros_willei
- Climacodium_biconcavum
- Climacodium_frauenfeldianum
- Coccolithus_pelagicus
- Corethron_hystrix
- Corethron_pennatum
- Coronosphaera_mediterranea
- Coscinodiscus_centralis

- *Coscinodiscus_concinnus*
- *Coscinodiscus_granii*
- *Coscinodiscus_marginatus*
- *Coscinodiscus_oculusiridis*
- *Coscinodiscus_radiatus*
- *Coscinodiscus_wailesii*
- *Dactyliosolen_antarcticus*
- *Dactyliosolen_fragilissimus*
- *Detonula_confervacea*
- *Detonula_pumila*
- *Dictyocha_fibula*
- *Dinophysis_acuminata*
- *Dinophysis_acuta*
- *Dinophysis_argus*
- *Dinophysis_caudata*
- *Dinophysis_hastata*
- *Dinophysis_norvegica*
- *Dinophysis_ovum*
- *Dinophysis_tripos*
- *Diplopelta_asymmetrica*
- *Diplopelta_steinii*
- *Diplopsalis_lenticula*
- *Diplopsalopsis_bomba*
- *Discosphaera_tubifera*
- *Ditylum_brightwellii*
- *Ephemera_planamembranacea*
- *Ethmodiscus_gazellae*
- *Eucampia_cornuta*
- *Eucampia_zodiacus*
- *Eupyxidicula_turris*
- *Florisphaera_profunda*
- *Fragilariopsis_doliolus*
- *Fragilariopsis_kerguelensis*
- *Fragilariopsis_oceanica*
- *Gephyrocapsa_caribbeanica*
- *Gephyrocapsa_ericsonii*
- *Gephyrocapsa_muelleriae*
- *Gladiolithus_flabellatus*
- *Gonyaulax_digitalis*
- *Gonyaulax_elongata*
- *Gonyaulax_pacifica*
- *Gonyaulax_polygramma*
- *Gonyaulax_spinifera*
- *Grammatophora_marina*
- *Guinardia_cylindrus*
- *Guinardia_delicatula*
- *Guinardia_flaccida*
- *Guinardia_striata*
- *Gymnodinium_gracile*
- *Gyrodinium_fusiforme*

- Gyrodinium_spirale
- Haslea_wawriake
- Helicosphaera_carteri
- Helicotheca_tamesis
- Hemiaulus_chinensis
- Hemiaulus_hauckii
- Hemiaulus_membranaceus
- Hemidiscus_cuneiformis
- Impagidinium_aculeatum
- Impagidinium_patulum
- Impagidinium_sphaericum
- Kofoidinium_velleloides
- Lauderia_annulata
- Leonella_granifera
- Leptocylindrus_danicus
- Leptocylindrus_mediterraneus
- Leptocylindrus_minimus
- Leucocryptos_marina
- Licmophora_abbreviata
- Lingulodinium_polyedra
- Lioloma_delicatulum
- Lioloma_pacificum
- Lithodesmium_undulatum
- Mastogloia_rostrata
- Membraneis_challengeri
- Mesoporos_perforatus
- Meuniera_membranacea
- Neocalyptrella_robusta
- Nitzschia_bicapitata
- Nitzschia_bilobata
- Nitzschia_longissima
- Nitzschia_pacifica
- Octactis_speculum
- Odontella_aurita
- Odontella_longicruris
- Oolithotus_fragilis
- Ophiaster_hydroideus
- Ornithocercus_magnificus
- Ornithocercus_quadratus
- Ornithocercus_steinii
- Ornithocercus_thumii
- Oxytoxum_laticeps
- Oxytoxum_scolopax
- Oxytoxum_variabile
- Paralia_sulcata
- Pentapharsodinium_dalei
- Phaeocystis_pouchetii
- Phalacroma_mitra
- Phalacroma_oxytoxoides
- Phalacroma_rapa

- *Phalacroma_rotundatum*
- *Planktoniella_sol*
- *Podolampas_bipes*
- *Podolampas_palmipes*
- *Podolampas_spinifera*
- *Polykrikos_schwartzii*
- *Preperidinium_meunieri*
- *Proboscia_indica*
- *Proboscia_inermis*
- *Proboscia_truncata*
- *Pronoctiluca_pelagica*
- *Pronoctiluca_spinifera*
- *Prorocentrum_balticum*
- *Prorocentrum_cordatum*
- *Prorocentrum_dentatum*
- *Prorocentrum_gracile*
- *Prorocentrum_lima*
- *Prorocentrum_micans*
- *Prorocentrum_rostratum*
- *Protoceratium_reticulatum*
- *Protoperidinium_bipes*
- *Protoperidinium_brevipes*
- *Protoperidinium_brochii*
- *Protoperidinium_cerasus*
- *Protoperidinium_claudicans*
- *Protoperidinium_conicoides*
- *Protoperidinium_crassipes*
- *Protoperidinium_curtipes*
- *Protoperidinium_depressum*
- *Protoperidinium_diabolus*
- *Protoperidinium_divergens*
- *Protoperidinium_elegans*
- *Protoperidinium_excentricum*
- *Protoperidinium_fatulipes*
- *Protoperidinium_grande*
- *Protoperidinium_granii*
- *Protoperidinium_leonis*
- *Protoperidinium_longipes*
- *Protoperidinium_longispinum*
- *Protoperidinium_mendiolae*
- *Protoperidinium_oblongum*
- *Protoperidinium_obtusum*
- *Protoperidinium_oceanicum*
- *Protoperidinium_ovatum*
- *Protoperidinium_pallidum*
- *Protoperidinium_pellucidum*
- *Protoperidinium_pentagonum*
- *Protoperidinium_peruvianum*
- *Protoperidinium_pyrum*
- *Protoperidinium_quarnerense*

- *Protoperidinium_steinii*
- *Protoperidinium_subinerme*
- *Protoperidinium_tenuissimum*
- *Protoperidinium_tristylum*
- *Pseudonitzschia_delicatissima*
- *Pseudonitzschia_lineola*
- *Pseudonitzschia_pungens*
- *Pseudonitzschia_serjata*
- *Pseudosolenia_calcaravis*
- *Ptychodiscus_noctiluca*
- *Pyrocystis_elegans*
- *Pyrocystis_fusififormis*
- *Pyrophacus_horologium*
- *Pyrophacus_steinii*
- *Rhabdolithes_claviger*
- *Rhizosolenia_acuminata*
- *Rhizosolenia_bergonii*
- *Rhizosolenia_castracanei*
- *Rhizosolenia_chunii*
- *Rhizosolenia_cleveii*
- *Rhizosolenia_formosa*
- *Rhizosolenia_hebetata*
- *Rhizosolenia_hyalina*
- *Rhizosolenia_imbricata*
- *Rhizosolenia_setigera*
- *Rhizosolenia_temperei*
- *Roperia_tesselata*
- *Scrippsiella_acuminata*
- *Skeletonema_costatum*
- *Spiraulax_kofoidii*
- *Stephanopyxis_palmeriana*
- *Syracosphaera_nodosa*
- *Syracosphaera_pulchra*
- *Thalassionema_bacillare*
- *Thalassionema_frauenfeldii*
- *Thalassionema_nitzschioides*
- *Thalassiosira_aestivalis*
- *Thalassiosira_angulata*
- *Thalassiosira_angustelineata*
- *Thalassiosira_decipiens*
- *Thalassiosira_eccentrica*
- *Thalassiosira_gracilis*
- *Thalassiosira_gravida*
- *Thalassiosira_leptopus*
- *Thalassiosira_mendiolana*
- *Thalassiosira_nordenskioldii*
- *Thalassiosira_partheneia*
- *Thalassiosira_subtilis*
- *Thalassiothrix_heteromorpha*
- *Thalassiothrix_longissima*

- *Thoracosphaera_heimii*
- *Triadinium_polyedricum*
- *Trieres_chinensis*
- *Trieres_mobiliensis*
- *Tripes_azoricus*
- *Tripes_belone*
- *Tripes_bucephalus*
- *Tripes_buceros*
- *Tripes_candelabrum*
- *Tripes_carriensis*
- *Tripes_compressus*
- *Tripes_concilians*
- *Tripes_contortus*
- *Tripes_deflexus*
- *Tripes_dens*
- *Tripes_euarquatus*
- *Tripes_eugrammus*
- *Tripes_extensus*
- *Tripes_furca*
- *Tripes_fusus*
- *Tripes_gravidus*
- *Tripes_hexacanthus*
- *Tripes_incisus*
- *Tripes_inflatus*
- *Tripes_karstenii*
- *Tripes_kofoidii*
- *Tripes_lamellicornis*
- *Tripes_limulus*
- *Tripes_lineatus*
- *Tripes_longipes*
- *Tripes_lunula*
- *Tripes_macroceros*
- *Tripes_minutus*
- *Tripes_muelleri*
- *Tripes_pentagonus*
- *Tripes_platycornis*
- *Tripes_pulchellus*
- *Tripes_ranipes*
- *Tripes_strictus*
- *Tripes_teres*
- *Tripes_vultur*
- *Tryblionella_compressa*
- *Umbellosphaera_irregularis*
- *Umbellosphaera_tenuis*
- *Umbilicosphaera_hulburtiana*
- *Umbilicosphaera_sibogae*
- *Ditrichocorycaeus_anglicus*
- *Abyla_trigona*
- *Abylopsis_eschscholtzii*
- *Abylopsis_tetragona*

- *Acartia_Acartia_danae*
- *Acartia_Acartia_negligens*
- *Acartia_Acartiura_clausi*
- *Acartia_Acartiura_longiremis*
- *Acartia_Acartiura_tranteri*
- *Acartia_Odontacartia_erythraea*
- *Acrocalanus_gibber*
- *Acrocalanus_gracilis*
- *Acrocalanus_longicornis*
- *Acrocalanus_monachus*
- *Aegina_citrea*
- *Aeginopsis_laurentii*
- *Aetideopsis_armatus*
- *Aetideopsis_minor*
- *Aetideopsis_rostrata*
- *Aetideus_acutus*
- *Aetideus_armatus*
- *Aetideus_giesbrechti*
- *Aetideus_pacificus*
- *Agalma_elegans*
- *Agalma_okenii*
- *Agetus_flaccus*
- *Agetus_typicus*
- *Aglantha_digitale*
- *Aglaura_hemistoma*
- *Aidanosagitta_crassa*
- *Aidanosagitta_neglecta*
- *Aidanosagitta_regularis*
- *Amallothrix_tenuiserrata*
- *Amphicaryon_acaule*
- *Amphicaryon_ernesti*
- *Amphicaryon_peltifera*
- *Anchylomera_blossevillei*
- *Anomalocera_patersoni*
- *Augaptilus_glacialis*
- *Augaptilus_longicaudatus*
- *Bassia_bassensis*
- *Beroe_cucumis*
- *Brachyscelus_crusculum*
- *Calanoides_acutus*
- *Calanoides_carinatus*
- *Calanopia_elliptica*
- *Calanus_agulhensis*
- *Calanus_australis*
- *Calanus_finmarchicus*
- *Calanus_glacialis*
- *Calanus_helgolandicus*
- *Calanus_hyperboreus*
- *Calanus_marshallae*
- *Calanus_pacificus*

- Calanus_propinquus
- Calanus_simillimus
- Calocalanus_contractus
- Calocalanus_elegans
- Calocalanus_gracilis
- Calocalanus_neptunus
- Calocalanus_pavo
- Calocalanus_pavoninus
- Calocalanus_plumatus
- Calocalanus_plumulosus
- Calocalanus_styliremis
- Calocalanus_tenuis
- Candacia_armata
- Candacia_bipinnata
- Candacia_bispinosa
- Candacia_catula
- Candacia_columbiae
- Candacia_curta
- Candacia_ethiopica
- Candacia_longimana
- Candacia_maxima
- Candacia_pachydactyla
- Candacia_simplex
- Candacia_truncata
- Canthocalanus_pauper
- Cavolinia_inflexa
- Cavolinia_uncinata
- Centropages_abdominalis
- Centropages_bradyi
- Centropages_chierchiae
- Centropages_furcatus
- Centropages_gracilis
- Centropages_hamatus
- Centropages_orsinii
- Centropages_typicus
- Centropages_violaceus
- Ceratocymba_leuckartii
- Ceratocymba_sagittata
- Chelophyes_appendiculata
- Chelophyes_contorta
- Chiridius_gracilis
- Chiridius_obtusifrons
- Chiridius_poppei
- Chirundina_streetsii
- Chuniphyes_multidentata
- Clausocalanus_arcuicornis
- Clausocalanus_brevipes
- Clausocalanus_farrani
- Clausocalanus_furcatus
- Clausocalanus_ingens

- *Clausocalanus_jobei*
- *Clausocalanus_laticeps*
- *Clausocalanus_lividus*
- *Clausocalanus_mastigophorus*
- *Clausocalanus_parapergens*
- *Clausocalanus_paululus*
- *Clausocalanus_pergens*
- *Clausophyes_moserae*
- *Clio_pyramidata*
- *Colobonema_sericeum*
- *Copilia_mediterranea*
- *Copilia_mirabilis*
- *Copilia_quadrata*
- *Corycaeus_clausi*
- *Corycaeus_crassiusculus*
- *Corycaeus_speciosus*
- *Cosmocalanus_darwinii*
- *Creseis_clava*
- *Creseis_conica*
- *Creseis_virgula*
- *Ctenocalanus_citer*
- *Ctenocalanus_vanus*
- *Cyllopus_lucasii*
- *Cymbulia_peronii*
- *Decipisagitta_decipiens*
- *Delibus_nudus*
- *Dentigloborotalia_anfracta*
- *Desmophyes_annectens*
- *Diacavolinia_longirostris*
- *Diacria_quadridentata*
- *Diacria_trispinosa*
- *Dimophyes_arctica*
- *Diphyes_bojani*
- *Diphyes_dispar*
- *Ditrichocorycaeus_dahli*
- *Doliolum_denticulatum*
- *Enneagonum_hyalinum*
- *Euaugaptilus_hecticus*
- *Eucalanus_bungii*
- *Eucalanus_hyalinus*
- *Eucalanus_inermis*
- *Euchaeta_acuta*
- *Euchaeta_concinna*
- *Euchaeta_indica*
- *Euchaeta_longicornis*
- *Euchaeta_marina*
- *Euchaeta_media*
- *Euchaeta_rimana*
- *Euchirella_amoena*
- *Euchirella_curticauda*

- *Euchirella_messinensis*
- *Euchirella_rostrata*
- *Euchirella_rostromagna*
- *Eudoxoides_mitra*
- *Eudoxoides_spiralis*
- *Eukrohnia_hamata*
- *Euphausia_americana*
- *Euphausia_brevis*
- *Euphausia_crystallorophias*
- *Euphausia_frigida*
- *Euphausia_gibba*
- *Euphausia_gibboides*
- *Euphausia_hemigibba*
- *Euphausia_krohnii*
- *Euphausia_longirostris*
- *Euphausia_mucronata*
- *Euphausia_mutica*
- *Euphausia_pacifica*
- *Euphausia_recurva*
- *Euphausia_similis*
- *Euphausia_superba*
- *Euphausia_tenera*
- *Euphausia_triacantha*
- *Euphausia_vallentini*
- *Farranula_concinna*
- *Farranula_gibbula*
- *Farranula_gracilis*
- *Farranula_rostrata*
- *Ferosagitta_ferox*
- *Ferosagitta_robusta*
- *Flaccisagitta_enflata*
- *Flaccisagitta_hexaptera*
- *Fritillaria_borealis*
- *Fritillaria_pellucida*
- *Gaetanus_brevispinus*
- *Gaetanus_minor*
- *Gaetanus_tenuispinus*
- *Geryonia_proboscidalis*
- *Globigerina_bulloides*
- *Globigerina_falconensis*
- *Globigerinella_calida*
- *Globigerinella_siphonifera*
- *Globigerinita_glutinata*
- *Globigerinita_minuta*
- *Globigerinita_uvula*
- *Globigerinoides_conglobatus*
- *Globigerinoides_ruber*
- *Globigerinoides_tenellus*
- *Globoconella_inflata*
- *Globorotalia_hirsuta*

- *Globorotalia_menardii*
- *Globorotalia_scitula*
- *Globorotalia_truncatulinoides*
- *Globoturborotalita_rubescens*
- *Halistemma_rubrum*
- *Haloptilus_acutifrons*
- *Haloptilus_longicornis*
- *Haloptilus_ocellatus*
- *Haloptilus_ornatus*
- *Haloptilus_oxycephalus*
- *Haloptilus_spiniceps*
- *Hastigerina_pelagica*
- *Heliconoides_inflatus*
- *Heteropyramis_maculata*
- *Heterorhabdus_austrinus*
- *Heterorhabdus_norvegicus*
- *Heterorhabdus_papilliger*
- *Heterorhabdus_spinifer*
- *Heterorhabdus_spinifrons*
- *Heterorhabdus_tanneri*
- *Heterostylites_longicornis*
- *Hippopodius_hippopus*
- *Hyalocylis_striata*
- *Hyperia_galba*
- *Hyperia_medusarum*
- *Hyperiella_dilatata*
- *Hyperoche_medusarum*
- *Ihleia_racovitzai*
- *Isias_clavipes*
- *Jaschnovia_tolli*
- *Krohnitta_pacifica*
- *Krohnitta_subtilis*
- *Labidocera_acuta*
- *Labidocera_acutifrons*
- *Lensia_achilles*
- *Lensia_campanella*
- *Lensia_conoidea*
- *Lensia_cossack*
- *Lensia_fowleri*
- *Lensia_grimaldi*
- *Lensia_hotspur*
- *Lensia_meteori*
- *Lensia_multicristata*
- *Lensia_pannikari*
- *Lensia_subtilis*
- *Lensia_subtiloides*
- *Limacina_bulimoides*
- *Limacina_helicina*
- *Limacina_lesueurii*
- *Limacina_retroversa*

- *Limacina_trochiformis*
- *Liriope_tetraphylla*
- *Lucicutia_clausi*
- *Lucicutia_curta*
- *Lucicutia_flavicornis*
- *Lucicutia_gaussae*
- *Lucicutia_gemina*
- *Lucicutia_ovalis*
- *Mecynocera_clausi*
- *Meganyctiphanes_norvegica*
- *Mesocalanus_tenuicornis*
- *Mesosagitta_minima*
- *Metridia_curticauda*
- *Metridia_gerlachei*
- *Metridia_longa*
- *Metridia_lucens*
- *Metridia_okhotensis*
- *Metridia_pacifica*
- *Metridia_venusta*
- *Microcalanus_pusillus*
- *Microcalanus_pygmaeus*
- *Mimocalanus_cultrifer*
- *Monothula_subtilis*
- *Muggiaea_atlantica*
- *Muggiaea_kochii*
- *Nannocalanus_minor*
- *Nanomia_bijuga*
- *Nectopyramis_thetis*
- *Nematobrachion_boopis*
- *Nematobrachion_flexipes*
- *Nematobrachion_sexspinosum*
- *Nematoscelis_atlantica*
- *Nematoscelis_difficilis*
- *Nematoscelis_megalops*
- *Nematoscelis_microps*
- *Neocalanus_cristatus*
- *Neocalanus_gracilis*
- *Neocalanus_plumchrus*
- *Neocalanus_robustior*
- *Neocalanus_tonsus*
- *Neogloboquadrina_dutertrei*
- *Neogloboquadrina_incompta*
- *Neogloboquadrina_pachyderma*
- *Nullosetigera_helgae*
- *Nyctiphanes_australis*
- *Oikopleura_Coecaria_longicauda*
- *Oikopleura_Vexillaria_dioica*
- *Oikopleura_Vexillaria_labradoriensis*
- *Oikopleura_Vexillaria_vanhoeffeni*
- *Oithona_atlantica*

- *Oithona_decipiens*
- *Oithona_fallax*
- *Oithona_frigida*
- *Oithona_nana*
- *Oithona_parvula*
- *Oithona_plumifera*
- *Oithona_robusta*
- *Oithona_setigera*
- *Oithona_similis*
- *Oithona_simplex*
- *Oithona_vivida*
- *Oncaea_curta*
- *Oncaea_curvata*
- *Oncaea_media*
- *Oncaea_mediterranea*
- *Oncaea_notopus*
- *Oncaea_ornata*
- *Oncaea_ovalis*
- *Oncaea_parila*
- *Oncaea_venusta*
- *Onychocorycaeus_agilis*
- *Onychocorycaeus_giesbrechti*
- *Onychocorycaeus_ovalis*
- *Orbulina_universa*
- *Oxycephalus_clausi*
- *Pantachogon_haeckeli*
- *Paracalanus_aculeatus*
- *Paracalanus_denudatus*
- *Paracalanus_indicus*
- *Paracalanus_nanus*
- *Paracalanus_parvus*
- *Paraeuchaeta_antarctica*
- *Paraeuchaeta_biloba*
- *Paraeuchaeta_elongata*
- *Paraeuchaeta_exigua*
- *Paraeuchaeta_glacialis*
- *Paraeuchaeta_gracilis*
- *Paraeuchaeta_hebes*
- *Paraeuchaeta_norvegica*
- *Paraeuchaeta_tonsa*
- *Paraheterorhabdus_compactus*
- *Paraheterorhabdus_farrani*
- *Parasagitta_elegans*
- *Pareucalanus_attenuatus*
- *Pareucalanus_sewelli*
- *Parvocalanus_latus*
- *Pegantha_martagon*
- *Pegea_confoederata*
- *Pelagia_noctiluca*
- *Periphylla_periphylla*

- *Phaenna_spinifera*
- *Phronima_sedentaria*
- *Phrosina_semilunata*
- *Physophora_hydrostatica*
- *Pleurobrachia_pileus*
- *Pleuromamma_abdominalis*
- *Pleuromamma_borealis*
- *Pleuromamma_gracilis*
- *Pleuromamma_indica*
- *Pleuromamma_piseki*
- *Pleuromamma_robusta*
- *Pleuromamma_scutullata*
- *Pleuromamma_xiphias*
- *Pontellina_plumata*
- *Praya_dubia*
- *Primno_abyssalis*
- *Primno_macropa*
- *Pseudoamallothrix_cenotelis*
- *Pseudoamallothrix_ovata*
- *Pseudocalanus_elongatus*
- *Pseudocalanus_minutus*
- *Pseudosagitta_gazellae*
- *Pseudosagitta_lyra*
- *Pseudosagitta_maxima*
- *Pterosagitta_draco*
- *Pulleniatina_obliquiloculata*
- *Pyrosoma_atlanticum*
- *Racovitzanus_antarcticus*
- *Rhincalanus_cornutus*
- *Rhincalanus_gigas*
- *Rhincalanus_nasutus*
- *Rhopalonema_velatum*
- *Rosacea_cymbiformis*
- *Rosacea_plicata*
- *Sagitta_bipunctata*
- *Salpa_aspera*
- *Salpa_fusififormis*
- *Salpa_maxima*
- *Salpa_thompsoni*
- *Sapphirina_angusta*
- *Sapphirina_metallina*
- *Sapphirina_nigromaculata*
- *Sapphirina_opalina*
- *Scaphocalanus_brevicornis*
- *Scaphocalanus_curtus*
- *Scaphocalanus_echinatus*
- *Scaphocalanus_farrani*
- *Scaphocalanus_magnus*
- *Scaphocalanus_vervoorti*
- *Scina_borealis*

- *Scolecithricella_abyssalis*
- *Scolecithricella_dentata*
- *Scolecithricella_marginata*
- *Scolecithricella_minor*
- *Scolecithricella_vittata*
- *Scolecithrix_bradyi*
- *Scolecithrix_danae*
- *Scolecitrichopsis_ectenopus*
- *Scottocalanus_securifrons*
- *Serratosagitta_pacifica*
- *Serratosagitta_pseudoserratodentata*
- *Serratosagitta_serratodentata*
- *Serratosagitta_tasmanica*
- *Soestia_zonaria*
- *Solidosagitta_marri*
- *Solidosagitta_zetesios*
- *Solmundella_bitentaculata*
- *Spinocalanus_abyssalis*
- *Spinocalanus_antarcticus*
- *Spinocalanus_longicornis*
- *Spinocalanus_magnus*
- *Spinocalanus_terranovae*
- *Stephos_longipes*
- *Styliola_subula*
- *Stylocheiron_abbreviatum*
- *Stylocheiron_affine*
- *Stylocheiron_carinatum*
- *Stylocheiron_elongatum*
- *Stylocheiron_longicorne*
- *Stylocheiron_maximum*
- *Stylocheiron_robustum*
- *Stylocheiron_suhmi*
- *Subeucalanus_crassus*
- *Subeucalanus_longiceps*
- *Subeucalanus_monachus*
- *Subeucalanus_mucronatus*
- *Subeucalanus_pileatus*
- *Subeucalanus_subcrassus*
- *Subeucalanus_subtenuis*
- *Sulculeolaria_biloba*
- *Sulculeolaria_chuni*
- *Sulculeolaria_monoica*
- *Sulculeolaria_quadri-valvis*
- *Sulculeolaria_turgida*
- *Temora_discaudata*
- *Temora_longicornis*
- *Temora_stylifera*
- *Temora_turbinata*
- *Temorites_brevis*
- *Temoropia_mayumbaensis*

- *Tessarabrachion_oculatum*
- *Thalia_democratica*
- *Thalia_orientalis*
- *Themisto_abysorum*
- *Themisto_compressa*
- *Themisto_gaudichaudii*
- *Themisto_libellula*
- *Themisto_pacifica*
- *Thetys_vagina*
- *Thielea_helicoides*
- *Thysanoessa_gregaria*
- *Thysanoessa_inermis*
- *Thysanoessa_inspinata*
- *Thysanoessa_longicaudata*
- *Thysanoessa_longipes*
- *Thysanoessa_macrura*
- *Thysanoessa_raschii*
- *Thysanoessa_spiniifera*
- *Thysanopoda_acutifrons*
- *Thysanopoda_aequalis*
- *Thysanopoda_cristata*
- *Thysanopoda_microphthalma*
- *Thysanopoda_obtusifrons*
- *Thysanopoda_pectinata*
- *Thysanopoda_tricuspidata*
- *Triconia_antarctica*
- *Triconia_borealis*
- *Triconia_conifera*
- *Triconia_dentipes*
- *Triconia_minuta*
- *Triconia_similis*
- *Trilobatus_sacculifer*
- *Turborotalita_humilis*
- *Turborotalita_quinqueloba*
- *Undeuchaeta_major*
- *Undeuchaeta_plumosa*
- *Undinula_vulgaris*
- *Urocorycaeus_furcifer*
- *Urocorycaeus_lautus*
- *Urocorycaeus_longistylis*
- *Vetoria_granulosa*
- *Vibilia_antarctica*
- *Vibilia_armata*
- *Vogtia_glabra*
- *Vogtia_pentacantha*
- *Vogtia_serrata*
- *Vogtia_spinosa*
- *Zonosagitta_bedoti*
- *Zonosagitta_nagae*
- *Zonosagitta_pulchra*

List of taxonomic entities AtlantECO-MAPS Collection #3

- Gamma.A
- HBD-02
- HBD-03
- HBD-04
- HBD-05
- HBD-06
- *Richelia intracellularis*
- *Trichodesmium erythraeum*
- *Trichodesmium thiebautii*
- UCYN.A1
- UCYN.A2
- UCYN.A
- UCYN.B
- UCYN.C